

1º filtro de seleção

Base: ACM

Total de artigos: 249

Artigos incluídos: 22 (CI1= 16, CI2= 6)

Artigos excluídos: 227 (CE1= 179, CE2= 0, CE3= 0, CE4= 38, CE5= 10, CE6= 0)

ID	Título	Link	Resumo	CI	CE	Motivo da exclusão
001	Model-based wireless health system design tool	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2448096.2448115	Well-being and fitness are major focuses pushing the need for a simple and effective method to monitor health. Researchers have pointed out safety, lifetime, and reliability as the key requirements of medical devices. Mismatch between requirements of wearable medical sensor and smart phone and their implementation is one of the major causes of failure. We demonstrate a Wireless Health System (WHS) design tool, which abstracts detail between model and implementation and generates sensor and smart phone code.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
002	Designing and developing an open source medical informatics module	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2382856.2382866	Lessons learned in planning and managing a development sprint to build a flexible, open source HL7 query service while successfully collaborating with diverse stakeholders and volunteers.	CI1		
003	An open source and web based framework for geographic and multidimensional processing	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/1141277.1141292	The development of Business Intelligence (BI) systems has been the destination of high investments made by several enterprises. The motivation is because an efficient decision support environment brings them several business world advantages, mainly if it provides integrated functionalities for the geographical and/or multidimensional processing. The intended goal is to provide users with a system capable of processing both geographic and multidimensional data in a seamless way, by abstracting the complexity of separately querying and analyzing these data in a decision making process. However, this integration may not be fully achieved yet or may be built using proprietary technologies. This paper presents an open source and web based framework for geographic and multidimensional decision support. Our approach uses a geographical data warehouse, a metadata source, a query language and a geographical and multidimensional engine for processing queries sent by a web based client application.		CE1	Não é da área da saúde.
004	Medical and health systems	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3233795.3233808	No abstract available.		CE4	Livro.
005	Design and Implementation of an Open Source 'Thin SIM' System for Collecting Data &	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3001913.3001923	Cutting edge communication technologies such as smartphones remain far from prevalent in most of the settings with the greatest need for improved health and development programs. As a result, designers of ICT4D initiatives often weigh difficult tradeoffs between the usability of smartphone applications for structured data collection versus the battery life, durability, cost and familiarity of basic phones. However, as this paper and our deployment experiences demonstrate, such tradeoffs are not always necessary. Most mobile network operators in sub-Saharan Africa offer value added services via simple, menu-driven applications that run directly	CI2		

	Supporting Global Health Care		from the SIM card. While conventional SIM applications can only be accessed by mobile network operators, this paper describes the design and implementation of a 'thin SIM' approach that does not require mobile network operator involvement. We have implemented this tool with more than 3,000 health workers and describe particular deployment experiences in Kenya, Benin, Nepal and Guatemala. We then reflect on a number of important limitations of the thin SIM approach, and opportunities for further development and deployment. Ultimately, we argue that there is an important role for SIM applications as one part of a configurable data collection toolkit for supporting global health and development programs.			
006	An open source cloud based platform for elderly health monitoring and fall detection	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3051488.3051513	The aim of this paper is to design and implement an open source e-health monitoring and fall detection system to monitor senior patients. The architecture of the system is based on a set of medical sensors and a microcontroller that communicates with a cloud. The sensors' data are collected and processed using a microcontroller, then, the data will be stored on a cloud to form a permanent record, as well as, to facilitate the diagnosis and the real-time monitoring for doctors, which plays a vital role in the patients' rehabilitation and healing process. To fulfill this, a web interface is created that gives doctors the authority to access all patients' medical records and monitor their health statuses. Furthermore, to detect whether the patient will suffer from unpredicted fall, a fall detection system is also considered. The system is composed of a microcontroller, voice recognition module, accelerometer and a gyroscope. By utilizing the information gathered from the previous sensors, a fall can be detected and an alert message can be sent to the medical personnel for immediate help and assistance.	CI1		
007	Real-time smart advisory health system	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3227609.3227686	This paper presents a novel hybrid distributed system whose main goal is to enable triage processing on available mobile devices and further propagation of the data and patient history. The injured persons' vital data are obtained from biosensors and are monitored using mobile applications. The system aims to ease the decision of priority in treatment, as well as to further monitor and alarm state change. We give overview of the system and we analyze the strengths and the weakness of the system given the hardware, software and communication components. We evaluate the system in different scenarios and we present the results.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
008	Coordinating e-health systems with TuCSoN semantic tuple centres	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/1964144.1964150	Open and distributed application scenarios like e-Health systems mandate for new coordination models and technologies. In particular, they require middleware providing coordination and security services modelled with abstractions promoting run-time observability and adaptation. Along this line, in this paper we describe the architecture of the TuCSoN coordination infrastructure, and show its application to an e-Health application scenario.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
009	Towards Responsible Data Practices in Digital Health: A case study of an open source	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3411763.3443438	In recent years, privacy and data rights have garnered growing attention in public discourse, policy making, and scholarly research. New data protection laws are being rolled out globally to codify data rights and ensure individual control over how personal data is shared and used. This evolving landscape presents several opportunities and challenges for healthcare. In this case study, we outline a design research agenda that emerged from the practical needs of an open source community focused on digital health software for community health in low- and middle-income countries. We situate this case study in the global landscape of data regulations, and the call for responsible data practices that go above and beyond regulatory		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.

	community's journey		compliance. We share findings from the formative stages of our multi-stage design process, which include a scoping literature review and a reframing of institutional policies and procedures. A primary contribution of our case study is that it offers an example of the institutional 'pre-work' necessary to make sense of the complex data protection landscape, and to chart a path forward for designing software that better supports responsible data practices. This case study also articulates the important role for digital health designers and implementers in operationalizing patient data rights.			
010	Field evaluation of a camera-based mobile health system in low-resource settings	https://doi.org/10.1145/2628363.2628366	The worldwide adoption of mobile devices presents an opportunity to build mobile systems to support health workers in low-resource settings. This paper presents an in-depth field evaluation of a mobile system that uses a smartphone's built-in camera and computer vision to capture and analyze diagnostic tests for infectious diseases. We describe how health workers integrate the system into their daily clinical workflow and detail important differences in system usage between small clinics and large hospitals that could inform the design of future mobile health systems. We also describe a variety of strategies that health workers developed to overcome poor network connectivity and transmit data to a central database. Finally, we show strong agreement between our system's computed diagnoses and trained health workers' visual diagnoses, which suggests that our system could aid disease diagnosis in a variety of scenarios. Our findings will help to guide ministries of health and other stakeholders working to deploy mobile health systems in similar environments.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
011	Patient health portal: a calendar paradigm	https://doi.org/10.1145/2316936.2316944	In this paper, we propose a conceptual model of a patient health portal based on a calendar paradigm. The study begins with a literature review on health portals and their stakeholders. Then, to support the proposed concept, we made an analysis of the state of the art in health portals and their main features. We propose a conceptual model for a user centered health portal and its needs. We also make an implementation of the conceptual model in an open source content management system (Drupal). Our study does also include the preliminary results of a survey to a group of key users.	CI1		
012	Demo of the medical device dongle: an open-source standards-based platform for interoperable medical device connectivity	https://doi.org/10.1145/2077546.2077565	Emerging medical applications require networked coordination between medical devices. However, most of the medical devices in use today do not support wireless communication or network connectivity. Currently, hospitals interested in coordinated medical care would have replace existing devices with expensive new devices. We believe that existing medical devices can be extended to support interoperable network connectivity. We demonstrate the Medical Device Dongle (MDD), an open-source platform that enables such extensions to current medical devices. The MDD can attach to any device that has a data output interface (RS-232 or USB) and enables it to connect wirelessly and in an interoperable manner for various applications. We show how multiple medical devices, including pulse oximeters and infusion pumps, can be connected and controlled together using an open-source platform, standards-based connectivity protocols, and model-driven software. The demo setup consists of medical devices attached to an MDD Agent, an MDD Manager device, and a mobile phone running monitoring applications. The MDD components can communicate over Bluetooth, WiFi and Ethernet.	CI1		
013	The medical device dongle: an open-source standards-based	https://doi.org/10.1145/2110363.2110438	Emerging medical applications require device coordination, increasing the need to connect devices in an interoperable manner. However, many of the existing health devices in use were not originally developed for network connectivity and those devices with networking capabilities either use proprietary protocols or implementations of standard protocols that are unavailable to the end user. The first set of devices are unsuitable for device coordination	CI1		

	sed platform for interoperable medical device connectivity		applications and the second set are unsuitable for research in medical device interoperability. We propose the Medical Device Dongle (MDD), a low-cost, open-source platform that addresses both issues.			
014	On the prioritization of data quality challenges in e-health systems in South Africa	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2815782.2815791	<p>Data quality is one of many challenges experienced in e-health. The collection of data with substandard data quality leads to inappropriate information for health and management purposes. Given evidence of challenges with regards to data quality in electronic health systems, the purpose of the study is to prioritise data quality challenges as experienced by data users of electronic healthcare systems in South Africa. The study adopted a sequential QUAL-quan mixed method research design towards the realisation of the research purpose. After carrying out a literature review on the background of e-health and the current status of research on data quality challenges, a qualitative study was conducted to verify and extend the theoretical list of data quality challenges. A quantitative study followed to prioritise data quality challenges as experienced by data users of electronic healthcare systems. Data users of electronic healthcare systems in South Africa served as the unit of analysis in the study. The data collection process included the conducting of interviews with four data quality experts to verify and extend the theoretical list of data quality challenges. This was followed by a survey targeting 100 data users of electronic healthcare systems in South Africa for which 82 responses were received. From the results of the study, a prioritised list of data quality challenges has been developed which can be applied to assist data users of electronic health care systems in South Africa to improve the quality of data in electronic healthcare systems. The most important data challenge is training. The prioritised list of data quality challenges allowed for evidence-based recommendations which can assist health institutions in South Africa to ensure future data quality.</p>		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
015	Implementation of SMART on FHIR in Developing Countries Through SFPBRF	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3301879.3301881	Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources (FHIR) is an International health standard for health data developed by Health Level Seven -- (HL7) an international organization for the development of health data standards. FHIR enables data interoperability as it is based on lightweight open source RESTful services. Many developed countries which already running electronic health record systems are now focused on the adoption of FHIR to unlock its potential benefits by integrating other technologies like Substitutable Medical Applications, Reusable Technology (SMART) platform. In most of the developing countries electronic health record system does not exist because they lag in resources to invest in electronic health record systems and they are still operating on paper-based health record system, so they are unable to adopt FHIR and other related technologies like SMART. Due to which, interoperability is not enabled on this paper-based data. These countries remain at a distance from the benefits of FHIR and SMART platform to provide better patient care to their patients, quick and efficient clinical decision making and better diagnostics. This paper presents the implementation of SMART on FHIR in healthcare organizations of developing countries through a proposed framework SFPBRF which not only maps paper-based health record system's data to HL7's FHIR standard but also integrate the complete SMART on FHIR platform to run SMART apps on this FHIR conformed data. This		CI1	

			paper presents successful translation (done by translation engine) of paper-based data to HL7 FHIR standard. It also shows the running of open source and internally developed SMART apps on this FHIR conformed data. Thus, by the successful mapping and implementation of SMART on FHIR through proposed framework SFPBRF we can conclude that FHIR can be adopted in healthcare organizations of developing countries and SMART on FHIR can help a lot in achieving better patient care, quick and efficient decision making and better diagnostics in developing countries.			
016	Harmonization of detailed clinical models with clinical study data standard	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2389672.2389678	Data sharing and integration between clinical research data management system (CDMS) and electronic health record (EHR) system remains a challenging issue. To deal with the challenge, there is emerging interest in utilizing the Detailed Clinical Modeling (DCM) approach across a variety of contexts. The Intermountain Healthcare Clinical Element Models (CEMs) have been adopted by the Office of the National Coordinator (ONC) awarded SHARPN project for normalizing patient data from the electronic medical records (EMRs). The objective of the present study is to describe our preliminary efforts on harmonization of the SHARPN CEMs with CDISC (Clinical Data Interchange Standards Consortium) clinical study data standards. We were focused on three generic domains: Demographics, Lab Tests and Medications. We performed a panel review on each data element extracted from the CDISC templates and SHARPN CEMs. We have identified a set of data elements that are common to the context of both clinical research and secondary use and discussed outstanding harmonization issues. We consider that the outcomes would be useful for defining new requirements for the DCM modeling community and ultimately facilitating the semantic interoperability between systems for both clinical research and secondary use.		CEI	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
017	Towards a test and validation framework for closed-loop physiology management systems for critical and perioperative care	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3357495.3357499	Many of medical devices come equipped with a communication interface. Over the years, there has been interest in leveraging these interfaces to add computers to the loop to aid in decision making and automatic application of interventions. Such systems, which we call Closed-Loop Assistants (CLAs), are intended to help clinicians manage the cognitive load that can arise as the complexity of patient management increases. We present an open-source framework for examining CLA-patient interactions through software simulations of the CLA with <i>in-silico</i> patients to enable early testing and validation of proposed physiology management strategies. We show how this framework can be used to test different strategies across a small patient population. Considering a patient population is important because inter-patient variability is one of the critical factors that can hamper the ability of a medical cyber-physical system like the CLA to meet its goals. The ability to explore this variability early in the design process therefore helps us in increasing robustness of the system.	CI1		
018	Data collection requirements for mobile connected health: an end user development approach	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3001854.3001856	The rise of smart mobile devices presents increasing opportunities for health monitoring outside the clinic. Through the use of sensors and wearables, innovative Connected Health applications can be developed. In particular, Digital Therapeutics (DT), a type of technology-enabled intervention, can be made possible through continuous data capture, aiding users through gaining feedback on their lifestyle choices and engagement with programs of recovery, and supplementing conventional treatments for chronic disease management such as in diabetes, epilepsy, and mental health. Unfortunately, patient-facing professionals capable of articulating appropriate sensor-enabled solutions, generally lack the full range of skills to develop such systems. A connected health application may involve mobile development, data services, visualisation, machine		CEI	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.

			learning, and sensor signal processing, needing multidisciplinary teams, including professional software engineers. The cost of maintaining a software team across the research and development stages may prove prohibitive for many, hindering innovation. This paper focuses on gathering requirements for <i>data collection</i> in mHealth studies, and reports the initial findings after a round of interviews with researchers in areas such as psychology, physiotherapy, neurology, and health promotion education. Those requirements are framed within an existing End User Development (EUD) tool to create mobile apps for the Android platform, the open source project MIT App Inventor. The survey results highlight not only the development work needed for App Inventor to be used as a data collection tool in DT, but also a number of potential security and privacy issues, and the implementation of a <i>layered</i> feedback loop with a social aspect at the heart of it.			
019	Enriching Technical Communication Education: Collaborating Across Disciplines and Cultures to Develop the piClinic Console	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3233756.3233929	I have observed that technical communication lessons with a real-world impact provide students with a more engaging learning experience. While this observation is consistent with the theory of adult learning, it is an ongoing challenge to keep the examples fresh from term to term. This report describes my experience developing the piClinic Console from the beginning of project in the spring of 2017 to the present. The piClinic Console is a low-cost, patient information system designed for use in limited-resource clinics in lower-middle-income countries. In addition to helping these clinics begin to automate their patient records, the project has provided opportunities to demonstrate and apply technical communication skills in a real-world context and has initiated inter-departmental and international collaborations. This experience report describes a brief history of how the project began, the design and educational lessons it has provided to our students, the collaborations it has encouraged, some lessons learned, and the plans for future development.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
020	Development and implementation of a loosely coupled, multi-site, networked and replicated electronic medical record in Haiti	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/1713254.1713272	Since 2005, we have been developing and implementing an electronic medical record (EMR) that supports both individual and population health care for HIV-infected patients in Haiti. The need to support countrywide monitoring and evaluation drove early architectural decisions to support linking systems under conditions of network uncertainty. Despite numerous challenges including frequent power outages and inadequate Internet access and support, the system (iSanté) is currently implemented in 55 clinic sites nationwide, tracks over 41,000 patients, and synchronizes patient data between in-country sites and the central site databases on a daily basis.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
021	The SMS-text adherence support (StAR) study: hardware and software	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2517899.2517931	This paper details the hardware and software infrastructure used to collect data and deliver a novel intervention in an on-going individually randomised three-arm parallel group trial in a resource-limited setting. The SMS-text Adherence support trial (StAR) tests the efficacy of a behavioural intervention delivered by SMS-text to support hypertension treatment adherence compared to usual care. The intervention is a structured program of clinic appointment and medication pick-up reminders, medication adherence support and hypertension-related education delivered remotely using an automated system of semi-tailored informational or interactive SMS-text messages delivered to the 1372 recruited participants. The technical infrastructure includes mobile		CI2	

	infrastructur e		device-based electronic data collection at the point of care with secure remote upload of the data; the intervention delivery system; real-time query identification for screening, enrolment and participant management procedures; and monitoring and evaluation of trial processes. We are using several open-source software platforms in conjunction with off-the-shelf hardware to set-up and run a randomised clinical trial of a novel intervention in a low-resource setting.			
022	Understandi ng the implementati on of an electronic hospital information system in a developing country: a case study from Pakistan	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.5555/1862795.1862803	Literature on implementation of hospital information systems is scarce, especially with regard to developing countries. Pakistan Institute of Medical Sciences (PIMS) is a large public sector hospital in Pakistan that successfully implemented a hospital information system (HIS). This article studies how this success was achieved and examines the hurdles faced in the implementation of the HIS and how they were overcome. The article aims to provide a better understanding of implementing HIS in a developing country setting, to add to academic knowledge in the area as well as to serve as a guide to anyone wishing to implement an HIS in such a setting.		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.
023	An Analytics Framework to Support Surge Capacity Planning for Emerging Epidemics	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2896338.2896354	Epidemics are a serious public health challenge, with epidemiologists and health analysts constantly trying to find more succinct ways to predict, and then prevent or minimize their impact. An important problem facing health systems is ensuring they are prepared for severe epidemics. Being able to predict an epidemic is only one part of the problem: resources need to be monitored in order to ensure their availability in the event of severe epidemics. Using System Dynamic modelling, health analysts can predict epidemics to a certain extent using previous infection dynamics, however mitigation strategies would be improved dramatically if the prediction was in real-time, utilizing the full potential of information from a range of sources: participatory surveillance systems, sentinel data from General Practitioners (GPs) etc. Using these techniques alongside Surge Capacity modelling allows the monitoring of resources for all areas of the health system, equipment levels, staff levels, and bed availability etc., ensuring better preparedness. This paper introduces a way to bring these concepts together, and highlights future work which will expand on these ideas allowing for the possible reallocation of resources in the event of shortage in some areas, and spare capacity in others.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
024	IORapp: An R tool for Inter-Observ er Reliability Assessment of Time and Motion data	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3452853.3452890	Direct observational time and motion studies, in which one or more observers continuously observe and record an individual's activities over a certain period of time, can provide valuable insights into work and communication patterns and assist in identification of areas to intervene to support safe and effective work. These studies have increased in number and sophistication, also due to the availability of software tools for PDA to support the observers. A key methodological issue for these studies is the assessment of Inter-Observer Reliability (IOR). IOR is crucial for ensuring reliability of data collection in which multiple observers are involved. In workflow time studies the multivariate, time-stamped and ordered nature of the data limits the applicability of traditional inter-rater reliability measures, and makes this assessment challenging. Measures such as Cohen's Kappa, in fact, are only applicable to one variable at the time, so that high K scores for one aspect can be achieved even if two observers disagree substantially		CE1	Não é da área da saúde.

			<p>on other variables which are the object of their observation. Secondly, computing these measures first requires either matching pairs of datapoints from different observers viewing the same entity, a problem that cannot be done with perfect certainty, or restructuring the data into fixed-length time window sequences. No single method can address all the different aspects on which observers in time and motion studies can disagree, so one should adopt a composite method. We developed a set of functions and a Shiny app to assist this process for data collected with the Work Observation Method By Activity Timing (WOMBAT) method. The app allows the loading of data from pairs/groups of observers and computes a wide set of agreement measures on both matched data and on time window data. These measures are presented in a dashboard along with interactive visualizations of the observers' data, and can be saved and plotted over time in a different section.</p>			
025	<p>Generality and reuse in a common type system for clinical natural language processing</p>	<p>https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2064747.2064755</p>	<p>The aim of Area 4 of the Strategic Healthcare IT Advanced Research Project (SHARP 4) is to facilitate secondary use of data stored in Electronic Medical Records (EMR) through high throughput phenotyping. Clinical Natural Language Processing (NLP) plays an important role in transforming information in clinical text to standard representation that is comparable and interoperable. To meet the NLP requirement of different secondary use cases of EMR, accommodate different NLP approaches, enable the interoperability between structured and unstructured data generated in different clinical settings, we define a <i>common type system</i> for clinical NLP that integrates a comprehensive model of clinical semantics with language processing types for SHARP 4. The type system has been implemented in UIMA (Unstructured Information Management Architecture), which allows for flexible passing of input and output data types among NLP components, and is available at the SHARP 4 website.</p>		CE1	<p>Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.</p>
026	<p>Generating Log Requirements for Checking Conformance against Healthcare Standards using Workflow Modelling</p>	<p>https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3290688.3290739</p>	<p>The healthcare industry establishes policies and standards to improve the quality of health processes and their delivery. Auditing and monitoring can be used to measure the quality of healthcare and check compliance with the health policies. Appropriate logging mechanisms can be considered as a key component to manage compliance initiatives because they can be used to monitor and audit low performance, malfunctions and unauthorised user activities. However, existing Health Information Systems (HISs) inadequately implement logging mechanisms, making it crucial to be improved for policy compliance. Identification of sufficient logging requirements is one of the major challenges faced by HIS developers. We present a step-wise workflow modelling approach to help identify logging requirements that can facilitate proper auditing against established typical patient journeys and documented healthcare policies and standards. As a case study we develop a healthcare event log file containing sufficient log details which has been merged from different hosts in a HIS in order to gather necessary log details to audit for policy compliance.</p>		CE1	<p>Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.</p>
027	<p>Febrl: a freely available record linkage system with a graphical</p>	<p>https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.5555/1385089.1385094</p>	<p>Record or data linkage is an important enabling technology in the health sector, as linked data is a cost-effective resource that can help to improve research into health policies, detect adverse drug reactions, reduce costs, and uncover fraud within the health system. Significant advances, mostly originating from data mining and machine learning, have been made in recent years in many areas of record linkage techniques. Most of these new methods are not yet implemented in current record linkage systems, or are hidden within 'black box' commercial software. This makes it difficult for users to learn about new record linkage techniques, as well as to compare existing linkage techniques with new ones. What is required are</p>	CI1		

	user interface		flexible tools that enable users to experiment with new record linkage techniques at low costs. This paper describes the <i>Febri</i> (Freely Extensible Biomedical Record Linkage) system, which is available under an open source software licence. It contains many recently developed advanced techniques for data cleaning and standardisation, indexing (blocking), field comparison, and record pair classification, and encapsulates them into a graphical user interface. <i>Febri</i> can be seen as a training tool suitable for users to learn and experiment with both traditional and new record linkage techniques, as well as for practitioners to conduct linkages with data sets containing up to several hundred thousand records.			
028	Personal MobileCoach: tailoring behavioral interventions to the needs of individual participants	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2968219.2972713	MobileCoach, an open source behavioral intervention platform, has been developed to provide health professionals with an authoring tool to design evidence-based, scalable and low-cost digital health interventions (DHI). Its potential meets the lack in resources and capacity of health care systems to provide DHI for the treatment of noncommunicable diseases. In the current work, we introduce the first personalization approach for MobileCoach with the purpose of identifying the needs of participants, tailoring the treatment and, as a consequence, enhancing the capability of MobileCoach-based DHIs. The personalization approach is then exemplified by a very first prototype of a DHI for people with asthma that is able to detect coughing by just using a smartphone's microphone. First empirical results with five healthy subjects and 80 coughs indicate its technical feasibility as the detection accuracy yielded 83.3%. Future work will focus on the integration of personalized sensing and supporting applications for MobileCoach.	CI1		
029	A survey and analysis of Electronic Healthcare Record standards	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/1118890.1118891	Medical information systems today store clinical information about patients in all kinds of proprietary formats. To address the resulting interoperability problems, several Electronic Healthcare Record standards that structure the clinical content for the purpose of exchange are currently under development. In this article, we present a survey of the most relevant Electronic Healthcare Record standards, examine the level of interoperability they provide, and assess their functionality in terms of content structure, access services, multimedia support, and security. We further investigate the complementarity of the standards and assess their market relevance.		CE5	Survey
030	Design and Development of a Patient-centric User Authentication System	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3386392.3399564	Advancements in computer and communication technology enabled the rapid growth of e-health services, which can nowadays provide various electronic methods (e.g., obtaining online consent, exchanging health data). In this context, user authentication is an essential security task within modern healthcare systems performed daily by millions of patients across the globe. Nevertheless, most e-health service providers often employ traditional text-based password solutions which result in increased cognitive load and often lead to poor usability and security. In this paper, we present the design and development of a patient-centric user authentication system, which offers a flexible, personalized and multi-factor user authentication solution to patients. The suggested solution is currently being implemented and evaluated within the EU Serums project - Securing Medical Data in Smart Patient-Centric Healthcare Systems, which is a research project supported by the European Commission (EC) under the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme (H2020).		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
031	Session details: Special Track	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.5555/2814058.3252439	No abstract available.		CE4	Conferência

	Applications and Tools				
032	Exploiting Bluetooth Vulnerabilities in e-Health IoT Devices	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3341325.3342000	Internet of Things (IoT) is an interconnected network of heterogeneous things through the Internet. The current and next generation of e-health systems are dependent on IoT devices such as wireless medical sensors. One of the most important applications of IoT devices in the medical field is the usage of these smart devices for emergency healthcare. In the current interconnected world, Bluetooth Technology plays a vital role in communication due to its less resource consumption which suits the IoT architecture and design. However Bluetooth technology does not come without security flaws. In this article, we explore various security threats in Bluetooth communication for e-Health systems and present some examples of the attacks that have been performed on e-Health systems by exploiting the identified vulnerabilities		CE1 Proposta de teste de segurança
033	Human Data Model: Improving Programmability of Health and Well-Being Data for Enhanced Perception and Interaction	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3402524	Today, an increasing number of systems produce, process, and store personal and intimate data. Such data has plenty of potential for entirely new types of software applications, as well as for improving old applications, particularly in the domain of smart healthcare. However, utilizing this data, especially when it is continuously generated by sensors and other devices, with the current approaches is complex—data is often using proprietary formats and storage, and mixing and matching data of different origin is not easy. Furthermore, many of the systems are such that they should stimulate interactions with humans, which further complicates the systems. In this article, we introduce the Human Data Model—a new tool and a programming model for programmers and end users with scripting skills that help combine data from various sources, perform computations, and develop and schedule computer-human interactions. Written in JavaScript, the software implementing the model can be run on almost any computer either inside the browser or using Node.js. Its source code can be freely downloaded from GitHub , and the implementation can be used with the existing IoT platforms. As a whole, the work is inspired by several interviews with professionals, and an online survey among healthcare and education professionals, where the results show that the interviewed subjects almost entirely lack ideas on how to benefit the ever-increasing amount of data measured of the humans. We believe that this is because of the missing support for programming models for accessing and handling the data, which can be satisfied with the Human Data Model .	CI2	
034	Modeling UIMA type system using web ontology language: towards interoperability among UIMA-based NLP tools	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2389672.2389679	With the recent development and adoption of NLP framework architectures, NLP modules/tools developed independently in the research community can be adopted as integrated applications. Development of wrappers and interfaces required to adopt NLP modules/tools, however, still requires huge amount of efforts. In this paper, we focus on one NLP framework architecture, UIMA (Unstructured Information Management Architecture), which defines annotations as types described in a type system and can achieve direct interoperability if a common type system is used. We explore the use of ontology to model UIMA types and argue existing ontology development or reasoning tools can be utilized to understand types (we use types and annotations interchangeably) from existing NLP systems developed under UIMA, define equivalent annotations in different NLP systems, and apply the practice in the ontology community to draw agreements on the definition of common NLP types, thereby achieving better interoperability among NLP modules/tools.		CE1 Não é da área da saúde.

035	Enhancing aspects of Thai chief complaint classification Performance	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3384613.3384630	In this paper, we describe the aspects affecting in our experimental results of classifying Thai chief complaint (ThCC) into ICD-10 code. By merging our proposed Thai word separator to machine learning-based classifiers, ThCC have been converted into ICD-10 code which stands for International Classification of Diseases, Tenth Revision, and is a standard code used by physicians and other healthcare professionals to identify all diagnoses, signs and symptoms. At the beginning of experiments, the dataset from the sign and symptom description ranged in group R00 to R69 of ICD-10 have been used for training the classifiers. Subsequently the classifiers have been applied to the test dataset represented by 150 chief complaint cases in order to assign the related ICD-10 codes, and to evaluate classification accuracy. The experiment achieves 85% precision, 76% F1-measure, and 71% recall using our proposed Thai word separator with Classification and Regression Trees (CART) technique. However, we need to increase the precision which is strong enough to support our proposed separator. The additional experiment has been done by adding 50 chief complaint cases to the test dataset. We also have applied our proposed techniques including conflict element finding and classification criteria setting to improve the precision. Consequently, the later experimental results get higher classification accuracy by decreasing the false positives to mitigate the low recall problem.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
036	An instantiation of a process model towards health interoperability	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3410886.3410911	In response to the critical problem of fragmentation of health information, a process model towards health interoperability is articulated. In conceptualizing and instantiating the research artifact, the DSR method was operationalized through the Mullarkey and Hevner elaborated Action Design Research (ADR) process model. The ADR process model was considered an appropriate choice as it caters for an immersive exploration as part of an in-situ context. This study articulated in this paper is considered to have a problem-centered entry point, as it is driven by the researcher-practitioner's desire to understand what a "better artefact would look like". The ADR process model is adopted, since it's iterative and in-situ nature is in line with the overreaching organizational research aim to develop a process model that can describe and guide the process of testing conformance of health information systems to the eHealth interoperability standards prescribed by the Health Normative Standards Framework in South Africa.		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.
037	Open data kit: tools to build information services for developing regions	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2369220.2369236	This paper presents Open Data Kit (ODK), an extensible, open-source suite of tools designed to build information services for developing regions. ODK currently provides four tools to this end: Collect, Aggregate, Voice, and Build. Collect is a mobile platform that renders application logic and supports the manipulation of data. Aggregate provides a "click-to-deploy" server that supports data storage and transfer in the "cloud" or on local servers. Voice renders application logic using phone prompts that users respond to with keypad presses. Finally, Build is a application designer that generates the logic used by the tools. Designed to be used together or independently, ODK core tools build on existing open standards and are supported by an open-source community that has contributed additional tools. We describe four deployments that demonstrate how the decisions made in the system architecture of ODK enable services that can both push and pull information in developing regions.		CE1	Não é da área da saúde.
038	The Development	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3340037.340039	Objective With the abundance of clinical data collection in modern digital hospitals, electronic health records (EHR) has become a tool for clinical and genomic research. In this study, we aim to make an aggregated EHR framework leveraging datasets either within or		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de

	of an Aggregated Electronic Health Record in Compliance with Consolidated Clinical Document Architecture		across consolidated clinical document architecture (C-CDA), and show its primary experiment results in a localized Chinese EHR development. Methods A total 53 templates released by China were integrated for this experiment, the aggregated EHR template construction was based on the existing mature international standards, the three-tier architecture ISO/HL7 CDA R2, and the HL7 RIM model. A series of tools were used in this experiment to integrate data from heterogeneous systems via C-CDA. Results After designing and modeling, the aggregated EHR could be displayed in html on the browser or XSLT-compatible application. The designed aggregated EHR document was composed of five layers such as document, component, section, entry, data element. Conclusions In conclusion, our proposed aggregated EHR in compliance with C-CDA framework could leverage EHR adoption efficiency in the future.			código-aberto.
039	Mining medical specialist billing patterns for health service management	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.5555/2449288.2449306	This paper presents an application of association rule mining in compliance in the context of health service management. There are approximately 500 million transactions processed by Medicare Australia each year. Among these transactions, there exist a small proportion of suspicious claims. This study applied association rule mining to examine billing patterns within a particular specialist group to detect these suspicious claims and potential fraudulent individuals. This work identified both positive and negative association rules from specialist billing records. All the rules identified were examined by a subject matter expert, a practicing clinician, to classify them into two groups, those representing compliant patterns and non-compliant patterns. The rules representing compliant patterns were then used to detect potentially fraudulent claims by examining whether claims are consistent with these rules. The individuals whose claims frequently break these rules are identified as potentially high risk. Due to the difficulty of direct assessment on high risk individuals, the relevance of this method to fraud detection is validated by analysis of the individual specialist's compliance history. The results clearly demonstrate that association rule mining is an effective method of identifying suspicious billing patterns by medical specialists and therefore is a valuable tool in fraud detection for health service management.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
040	Mobile! 2016: Proceedings of the 1st International Workshop on Mobile Development	https://dl.acm.org/doi/proceedings/10.1145/3001854	No abstract available.		CE4	Conferência.
041	3D technologies and the new digital ecosystem: a Brazilian experience	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2536146.2536187	3D technologies are ubiquitous in all domains of science and technology, ranging from the most simple product development, optimization and production to the more complex like aerospace industry. In a wide definition 3D technologies can be classified into virtual and physical. The virtual ones can provide computational models for many types of representation, simulation, optimization and scientific visualization. The physical 3D technologies are responsible to realize virtual models into real objects. When using a layer-by-layer deposition of material to build objects it is known as 3D printing or more technically additive manufacturing. This article presents an overview of the 3D technologies and the new paradigm for open hardware and software as well design exchange as a new	CI2		

			digital ecosystem that will strongly impact economy the next decades. It is also discussed three strategic programs and a community for medical imaging based on free software developed at CTL.			
042	A Framework for Teaching Security Design Analysis Using Case Studies and the Hybrid Flipped Classroom	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3289238	With ever-greater reliance of the developed world on information and communication technologies, constructing secure software has become a top priority. To produce secure software, security activities need to be integrated throughout the software development lifecycle. One such activity is security design analysis (SDA), which identifies security requirements as early as the software design phase. While considered an important step in software development, the general opinion of information security subject matter experts and researchers is that SDA is challenging to learn and teach. Experimental evidence provided in literature confirms this claim. To help solve this, we have developed a framework for teaching SDA by utilizing case study analysis and the hybrid flipped classroom approach. We evaluate our framework by performing a comparative analysis between a group of students who attended labs generated using our framework and a group that participated in traditional labs. Our results show that labs created using our framework achieve better learning outcomes for SDA, as opposed to the traditional labs. Secondary contributions of our article include teaching materials, such as lab descriptions and a case study of a hospital information system to be used for SDA. We outline instructions for using our framework in different contexts, including university courses and corporate training programs. By using our proposed teaching framework, with our or any other case study, we believe that both students and employees can learn the craft of SDA more effectively.		CE1	Não é da área da saúde.
043	Rendering patterns for enterprise applications	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2855321.2855344	Graphical User Interface (GUI) coding represents a significant amount of effort in Enterprise applications development. Due to the coupling between GUI screens and domain entities, GUI code is hard to reuse and has lots of duplicated chunks. We propose five rendering patterns to organize GUI artifacts based on domain model meta data of Enterprise applications. We have validated our approach by using evolution scenarios to compare the use of the proposed patterns with existing solutions, such as Scaffolding frameworks and AOM Rendering patterns.		CE1	Não é da área da saúde. Propõe padrões de interface para outro domínio de aplicação.
044	Session details: Special Track - Government Information Systems	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.5555/2814058.3252441	No abstract available.		CE4	Conferência.
045	On creating and sustaining alternatives: the case of Danish telehealth	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.7146/aahcc.v1i1.21297	This paper presents and discusses an initiative aimed at creating direct and long lasting influence on the use and development of telemedicine and telehealth by healthcare professionals, patients and citizens. The initiative draws on ideas, insights, and lessons learned from Participatory Design (PD) as well as from innovation theory and software ecosystems. Last, but not least, the ongoing debate on public finances/economy versus tax evasion by major private companies has been an important element in shaping the vision and creating support for the initiative. This vision is about democratic control, about structures for sustaining such control beyond initial design and implementation and about continued development		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.

			through Participatory Design projects. We see the "middle element", the structures for sustaining democratic control beyond initial design and implementation as the most important and novel contribution of the paper.			
046	On Architecture of BodyInNumbers Exercise and Wellness Health Strategy Framework	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3418094.3418102	They are many risk factors decreasing overall human physical and cognitive performance and increasing incidence of chronic diseases. It is very beneficial for any society to map, discuss and cope with these factors. This can be supported and evaluated by designing, developing, testing and using suitable self-management health systems. One of these systems is the BodyInNumbers exercise and wellness health strategy framework that allows experimenters to collect various heterogeneous health related data in a highly organized and efficient way. Thanks to its success and daily use, new requirements related to better security, scalability and maintainability of its architecture have emerged. The aim of this work is to present advances and changes in the architecture of the BodyInNumbers health strategy framework mainly focusing on new definition of user roles, optimization of the system deployment, and orchestration of the system components. As a proof of concept, a Kubernetes cluster prototype has been used to demonstrate the improved architectural solution.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
047	The Case for Community Health Innovation Networks: Note	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3209811.3212705	This commentary outlines the rationale for building community health innovation networks in settings of poverty and high burdens of disease. These networks integrate deep research expertise and sustained implementation infrastructure, with the aim of streamlining the design, building and scale up of evidence-based technical innovations for community health. Drawing on our experiences establishing such networks in Mali and Kenya, we discuss the importance of: 1) sustaining operational capacity to strengthen health systems; 2) being strategic about how we embed design research within ongoing implementation efforts; and 3) institutional partnerships that invest in infrastructure to support a series of studies and innovation efforts over time. Without claiming to offer any 'quick and easy' solutions, we argue that this approach has real potential to address the gap between research and practice in technical innovation for global health and sustainable development.		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.
048	Bridging the unstructured and structured worlds: an adaptive self learning medical form generating system	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2389672.2389684	The prevalence of medical report standards and structured reporting systems reflects the increasing demand for representing and preserving medical and clinical data with controlled vocabularies in well structured format. Strictly formatted medical reports offer high human readability and facilitate further data processing, such as querying, statistical analysis, and reasoning to support decision making. However, many medical reports, such as pathology reports, nursing notes and physician's notes, are written in free-text narration. Manually extracting free text reports by filling predefined data fields is cumbersome and error-prone. Meanwhile, information extraction tools try to automate such process, for example, through machine learning based methods. Such methods often require large volumes of training datasets annotated manually by humans, which is expensive to obtain. Furthermore, they are also limited by their accuracy (both precision and recall). To facilitate the process of extracting information from narrative medical reports and transforming extracted data into standardized structured forms, we present in this paper a semi-automatic system, ASLForm, that interacts with users, analyzes free text input and generates normalized answers to populate forms in real-time. This system learns from users' feedback transparently and establishes decision models incrementally. It requires no additional configurations and training datasets. ASLForm is not constrained to any domain, and is adaptable to free text input in any format. These features of the		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.

			system offer high usability and portability. Its design also enables easy integration with existing reporting systems.			
049	Participatory health information systems development in Cuba: the challenge of addressing multiple levels in a centralized setting	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/1011870.1011877	This paper will address issues of user participation in a large centralistic organization. It is based on one year experience of developing a computerized health information system within the Cuban health services. Relevant literature suggests that participative methods may be less feasible in centralistic environments. This paper confirms this by describing how participation in Cuba is restricted by political and organizational constraints. There is however documented that participatory approaches may be very rewarding where such constraints are overcome. Experiences from a broad range of health units and organizational levels in the Cuban project show a trend of weakening centralistic control with regard to hierarchical level and geographic distance, and thus more autonomous organizational units and participating individuals at lower level farther from Havana. The research reported is carried out within a framework of a larger network of similar health information projects being carried out in Africa and Asia, and the case of Cuba is being compared with experience from these countries.		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema
050	Analyzing the Impact of Inter-smell Relations on Software Maintainability: An Empirical Study with Software Product Lines	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3330204.3330254	A Software Product Line (SPL) consists of a systematic reuse strategy to construct systems with less effort as long as they belong to the same family that share the same components and belong to the same domain of Marketplace. In this context, to support large-scale reuse, components of a Software Product Line should be easy to maintain. Thus, developers should be more concerned with anomalies known as code smells and more than that, co-occurrences known as Inter-smell deserve to be further studied to verify their real impact on maintainability in SPL. Thus, this paper conducts a study to investigate the impact of Inter-smell occurrences on maintainability in MobileMedia and Health Watcher SPLs. The results show that the presence of co-occurrences of Inter-smell did not negatively impact the maintenance of MobileMedia and Health Watcher SPLs, unlike results found in other studies in the literature, and even more, our results indicate that the metric Lack of Cohesion of Methods is one of the most important for the maintainability of object-oriented SPLs.		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema
051	Smart Connect: last mile data connectivity for rural health facilities	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/1836001.1836006	In this paper we address the problem of providing data connection to the periphery of the health system by presenting Smart Connect. Smart Connect is a custom device that uses the cell phone network to provide limited data connectivity between a rural health facility and a server connected to the Internet. Through an analysis of the health systems in Nicaragua and Vietnam, we have identified a variety of processes that could be improved with this device. These include filing incidence reports on diseases, receiving results of diagnostic test, and providing automatic monitoring of vaccine refrigeration equipment. The main contributions of this work include a presentation of the Smart Connect requirements derived from the health care systems of Nicaragua and Vietnam, an argument in favor of facility based communication devices, and a brief discussion of the design for the Smart Connect device.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
052	Software Product Quality Evaluation Guide for Electronic	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3422392.3422478	Software product quality evaluation is an important process that benefits the system developer and the end user. Software products in domain specific, such as those in the health field, need specific treatments for their evaluation. This article presents a proposal for adaptations of a generic software product quality evaluation guide to evaluate a software domain specific. For the adaptations, the MEDE-PROS software product quality evaluation guide, the ISO/IEC 25010:2011, and the SBIS/CFM certification for electronic		CE1	Apresenta proposta de avaliação de qualidade de sistemas de saúde.

	Health Record Systems		health record (EHR) systems were used. The purpose of these adaptations was to obtain an update of the MEDE-PROS guide, allowing to inspect quality attributes in a EHR system. To demonstrate the applicability of the guide after the adaptations, two case studies were performed in three health information systems. With the preliminary results of the case study, it was checked that the adaptations made in the guide were consistent, updating the guide with the ISO/IEC 25010:2011 standard and making it specialist in EHR systems, contributing with system evaluation more effectively in both guide versions.			
053	Improved Data Accuracy Assessment Tool for Information Management Systems	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3442555.3442579	Developing countries are increasingly taking advantage of the rapid advancement in ICT to replace paper-based operations with Information Management Systems (IMS) such as District Health Information Software (DHIS). While the adoption of IMS presents significant benefits, challenges exist in the quality of IMS data. Inaccurate, incomplete or redundant data in IMS has misled organisations into making incorrect decisions leading to customer dissatisfaction and high cost implications. There is an urgent need for IMS stakeholders to have mechanisms of assessing the quality of data prior to data analysis, data sharing or decision making. Data Accuracy Assessment Tool (DAAT) assesses and identifies errors in a pair of context related datasets. DAAT provides ability for Data Managers to easily compare datasets by choosing attributes of their interest from a pool of diverse attributes that define the data. Through reports and visualization, the tool reveals the accuracy of data in real time using metrics such as validity, completeness and duplication of data. DAAT is scalable since it can be integrated with any IMS such as DHIS. The tool has been tested using four years Voluntary Medical Male Circumcision (VMMC) program data from JHPIEGO's AIDSFree project in Tanzania.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
054	Optimizing semantic MEDLINE for translational science studies using semantic web technologies	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2389672.2389683	Semantic MEDLINE provides comprehensive resources with structured annotations that have a potential to facilitate translational studies in the biomedical domain. It is computationally challenging, however, to perform queries directly from the data in the current Semantic MEDLINE database. In this research, we propose a domain pattern driven approach to optimize the Semantic MEDLINE data organization and representation for translational science studies using the Resource Description Framework (RDF) and Semantic Web technologies.		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.
055	Simulation of ISO/IEEE 11073 Personal Health Devices in WBANs	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3345768.3355939	Simulating new protocols for e-health systems is very important, as it allows an initial evaluation before a real implementation is made. On the other hand, network simulators do not offer proper support to represent medical applications or components to facilitate running simulations modeling e-health applications. The lack of simulators that specify the sensor type and its communication requirements make real experiments harder. Aiming at fulfilling this gap, this paper proposes the use of ISO/IEEE 11073 standard for Personal Health Devices (X73-PHD) in e-health network simulations, representing realistic medical applications and investigating the behavior of medical devices (sensors or actuators) in Wireless Body Area Network (WBAN) scenarios. We developed a free and open-source implementation of X73-PHD for Castalia Simulator, providing five different PHD types to act like real ISO/IEEE 11073 devices in WBAN simulations. Our implementation supports Agent-initiated mode, where PHDs take the initiative to send measurements to the hub. Our implementation also supports the unconfirmed communication mode and the confirmed	CI2		

			communication mode, where the receiver sends an acknowledgment to the sender every time it receives a packet. Simulation results showed that the confirmed communication mode did not perform well in WBANs when the interval between transmissions is too small, due to the long period of timeout proposed in the X73-PHD standard. Therefore, we propose a new extension to the confirmed mode standard that decreases the overhead of control packets over the network, using smaller timeouts and delivering more packets.			
056	Mobile phones for health education in the developing world: SMS as a user interface	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/1926180.1926197	Uganda suffers from a severe shortage of professional healthcare workers. Thus, programs aimed at prevention of disease are an important complement to the limited healthcare delivery system. We analyze two deployments of an SMS-based HIV/AIDS education system that uses a quiz format to assess people's knowledge of the disease, including its causes and methods of prevention. The deployments were to two groups in Uganda, one a sample of mobile phone users who live in a town in northwest Uganda; the other, workers at three factories in central and southeastern Uganda. The two samples had accuracy rates above chance levels and workers at the three factories had higher rates of participation (more individuals and more questions) than the sample selected from the cell tower service area. An analysis of incorrect answers suggested that while participants had some difficulty in matching the formatting required by the quiz, literacy did not appear to be a significant problem. We discuss the results in terms of implications for using SMS as a user interface mechanism and explore the possibility of using social ties among participants as a way to promote the scalability and sustainability of this quiz-based education method.		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.
057	Assessment of Machine Learning Security: The Case of Healthcare Data	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3460620.3460738	With technological advances and the use of the Internet everywhere, And the widespread use of machine learning has become important to pay attention to security in all areas of life, especially in the healthcare field, many concerns have arisen regarding the security of patient confidential data in health systems. As it became possible to change patient data, which would lead to a change in data accuracy or to data theft, which would lead to a violation of the safety system in the field of health care. In this paper, a health system was studied in a hospital in Jordan after collecting information on 769 records for pregnant diabetics. The analysis used Python to test the accuracy of this information and improve the performance of the model being created using machine learning algorithms, including decision trees and random forests. Since patient information in any health system has been exposed to many threats and weaknesses, the main goal was to reduce them, and obtain accurate information with good performance and excellent quality, to avoid compromising health rights and data protection for patients.		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema. Apresenta uma análise/avaliação de registros eletrônicos.
058	Setting up the mediboard HIS for use in hospital routine	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3368756.3369071	After conducting a comparative study of nine different open source hospital information systems (OSHIS): we used the DeLone & McLean model to evaluate the quality of information systems, and we used the SQALE method for the technical evaluation of source code, and we used the statistics published by Open Source communities referential to compare OSHIS related activities. We were able to choose MediBoard, which has a minimal technical debt of 42.16%. The activity statistics proved the potential of MediBoard with 2381 commits and 12 contributions in 2016. But this SIH would not yet have a standard usability. In fact, the current installation of MediBoard only allows 3 modules out of 63. To resolve this problem, we have used ISO 12207: the software life cycle standard, and we used ISO 14764: the software maintenance standard to have a complete and standard HIS. As a result, and after the implementation of our solution, we have been successful in making the usability of MediBoard standard.		CE1	Proposta de avaliação de qualidade do sistema.

059	Development of auxiliary functions: should you be agile? an empirical assessment of pair programming and test-first programming	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.5555/2337223.2337285	A considerable part of software systems is comprised of functions that support the main modules, such as array or string manipulation and basic math computation. These auxiliary functions are usually considered less complex, and thus tend to receive less attention from developers. However, failures in these functions might propagate to more critical modules, thereby affecting the system's overall reliability. Given the complementary role of auxiliary functions, a question that arises is whether agile practices, such as pair programming and test-first programming, can improve their correctness without affecting time-to-market. This paper presents an empirical assessment comparing the application of these agile practices with more traditional approaches. Our study comprises independent experiments of pair versus solo programming, and test-first versus test-last programming. The first study involved 85 novice programmers who applied both traditional and agile approaches in the development of six auxiliary functions within three different domains. Our results suggest that the agile practices might bring benefits in this context. In particular, pair programmers delivered correct implementations much more often, and test-first programming encouraged the production of larger and higher coverage test sets. On the downside, the main experiment showed that both practices significantly increase total development time. A replication of the test-first experiment with professional developers shows similar results.	CE1	Apresenta um estudo empírico.
060	Measuring Global Disease with Wikipedia: Success, Failure, and a Research Agenda	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2998181.2998183	Effective disease monitoring provides a foundation for effective public health systems. This has historically been accomplished with patient contact and bureaucratic aggregation, which tends to be slow and expensive. Recent internet-based approaches promise to be real-time and cheap, with few parameters. However, the question of when and how these approaches work remains open. We addressed this question using Wikipedia access logs and category links. Our experiments, replicable and extensible using our open source code and data, test the effect of semantic article filtering, amount of training data, forecast horizon, and model staleness by comparing across 6 diseases and 4 countries using thousands of individual models. We found that our minimal-configuration, language-agnostic article selection process based on semantic relatedness is effective for improving predictions, and that our approach is relatively insensitive to the amount and age of training data. We also found, in contrast to prior work, very little forecasting value, and we argue that this is consistent with theoretical considerations about the nature of forecasting. These mixed results lead us to propose that the currently observational field of internet-based disease surveillance must pivot to include theoretical models of information flow as well as controlled experiments based on simulations of disease.	CI2	
061	A semantic publish-subscribe coordination framework for IHE based cross-community health record exchange	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2537728.2537732	This paper presents a semantic agent coordination framework for the automatic exchange of Electronic Health Records (EHR). The framework enables health organizations that comply with the existing interoperability standards, as proposed by the Integrating Healthcare Enterprise (IHE), to dynamically connect in a P2P network. A set of autonomous agents and a set of distributed coordination rules are used to coordinate the agents in the search of specific health records. The framework models the interactions among the communities as a combination of the tuple centre agent communication model with the publish-subscribe paradigm and semantic web technologies. In order to illustrate the scalability of our approach, we evaluate the proposed solution in distributed settings. The contribution of this work is that it proposes the coordination mechanisms for IHE compliant communities to dynamically connect and share EHR of patients.	CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.

062	Toward semantic web based knowledge representation and extraction from electronic health records	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2064747.2064765	The recent large-scale deployment of Electronic Health Records (EHR) across medical institutions provides new opportunities of secondary use of EHR. One prerequisite of meaningful use of EHR data is interoperability among knowledge, data, and applications in healthcare IT. In this paper, we introduce our vision on applying semantic web techniques to clinical knowledge and data representation, as well as to retrieve useful information and knowledge from EHR. We discuss the challenges we are facing, as well as two real-world use cases we are currently working on.		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema
063	3D Stereo-lithographic models placed in Virtual Reality to assist in pre-operative planning	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3173519.3173522	Congenital heart disease is the most common congenital abnormality affecting 8 per 1000 children. Children with univentricular circulation undergo three staged procedures, the last of which is a Fontan procedure. In some children, the anatomical arrangement makes completion of the Fontan procedure highly complicated, and in some cases not possible, which may imply a serious morbidity or mortality for the child. Currently, echocardiography (ECG), cardiac magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) and computed tomography are used to define the preoperative cardiac anatomy. Five 3Dprinted hearts are already developed for Crumlin Hospital to assess the utility of preoperative 3D printing in assessment of patient suitability for Fontan procedure. The project described in this paper involves the development of 3D stereolithographic models of complex cardiac defects and place them in a VR headset for a medical team to be able to rehearse the surgical procedure.		CE1	Apresenta o desenvolvimento de um modelo 3D.
064	A peer to peer agent coordination framework for IHE based cross-community health record exchange	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2480362.2480617	This paper presents a Peer to Peer (P2P) agent coordination framework for the exchange of Electronic Health Records (EHR) between health organisations that comply with the existing interoperability standards as proposed by the Integrating Healthcare Enterprise (IHE). Every health organisation represents a community in a P2P network and uses a set of autonomous agents and a set of distributed coordination rules to coordinate the agents in the search of specific health records. To model the interactions among communities, the framework uses the tuple centre agent communication model and semantic web technologies. In order to illustrate the scalability of our approach, we evaluate the proposed solution in distributed settings.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
065	A framework for mobile disease report and investigation	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/1292331.1292368	This paper presents an application framework for mobile data acquisition and analysis applications that emphasizes reusability of code and design. The framework supports an embedded animal disease report and investigation system which includes a user interface, database persistence, and business logic on a system architecture which is cost-effective, robust, and platform-independent.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
066	Dynamic multiplex social network models on multiple time scales for simulating	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.5555/3242181.3242561	This contribution presents a model for dynamic networks of physical contacts among large populations and their application for reproducing complex patterns in epidemic spread. The networks are constructed from statistical data on demography, geography, organizational structure and contact behavior. Due to the heterogeneous nature of the data and by construction, rich topological characteristics such as overlapping communities, layering along multiple dimensions and multiplex dynamics on different time scales can be observed. The generated dynamic networks can furthermore be regarded as subgraphs or derivatives of latent social		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.

	contact formation and patterns in epidemic spread		networks. General results and observations from social network theory apply naturally and are used for explaining dynamic effects in epidemics. An exemplaric analysis investigates the impact of weak ties and effects of communities with decreased immunization on epidemic spread. Optimized implementation and visualization techniques turn out to be a key asset for dynamic simulation of contacts within large populations.			
067	MHealth Games as Rewards: Incentive or Distraction?	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3079452.3079459	Games may be employed for delivery of a clinical protocol, or as an incentive for protocol tasks. We focus on serious games in mHealth apps for pediatric patients with a chronic disease as an incentive for behavior modification. A patient is rewarded with enhanced gameplay in proportion to her/his compliance with a clinical protocol. The game-as-reward prevents fatigue and sustains patient engagement as the mHealth apps are used on a frequent basis when the affliction is a chronic disease. However, our experience shows a fine line between games that encourage engagement and ones that distract patients from protocol tasks.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
068	Cross-Modal Health State Estimation	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3240508.3241913	Individuals create and consume more diverse data about themselves today than any time in history. Sources of this data include wearable devices, images, social media, geo-spatial information and more. A tremendous opportunity rests within cross-modal data analysis that leverages existing domain knowledge methods to understand and guide human health. Especially in chronic diseases, current medical practice uses a combination of sparse hospital based biological metrics (blood tests, expensive imaging, etc.) to understand the evolving health status of an individual. Future health systems must integrate data created at the individual level to better understand health status perpetually, especially in a cybernetic framework. In this work we fuse multiple user created and open source data streams along with established biomedical domain knowledge to give two types of quantitative state estimates of cardiovascular health. First, we use wearable devices to calculate cardiorespiratory fitness (CRF), a known quantitative leading predictor of heart disease which is not routinely collected in clinical settings. Second, we estimate inherent genetic traits, living environmental risks, circadian rhythm, and biological metrics from a diverse dataset. Our experimental results on 24 subjects demonstrate how multi-modal data can provide personalized health insight. Understanding the dynamic nature of health status will pave the way for better health based recommendation engines, better clinical decision making and positive lifestyle changes.	CI1		
069	Relationships and data sanitization: a study in scarlet	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/1900546.1900567	Research in data sanitization (including anonymization) emphasizes ways to prevent an adversary from desanitizing data. Most work focuses on using mathematical mappings to sanitize data. A few papers examine incorporation of privacy requirements, either in the guise of templates or prioritization. Essentially these approaches reduce the information that can be gleaned from a data set. In contrast, this paper considers both the need to "desanitize" and the need to support privacy. We consider conflicts between privacy requirements and the needs of analysts examining the redacted data. Our goal is to enable an informed decision about the effects of redacting, and failing to redact data. We begin with relationships among the data being examined, including relationships with a known data set and other, additional, external data. By capturing these relationships, desanitization techniques that exploit them can be identified, and the information that must be concealed in order to thwart them can be determined. Knowing that, a realistic assessment of whether the information and relationships are already widely known or available will enable the sanitizers to assess whether		CE1	Não é da área da saúde.

			irreversible sanitization is possible, and if so, what to conceal to prevent desanitization.			
070	MVoice: a mobile based generic ICT tool	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2517899.2517940	Abundance of mobile phones in developing nations makes them an effective tool to spread information and communication technology. Currently different mobile based platforms are being used in a variety of ICT contexts in developing nations. These systems have been built with different features according to the context in which they are used. After studying existing tools, we have developed a generic mobile-based ICT tool, named MVoice, which can serve in multiple contexts with minimal configuration changes. Our tool can also be extended easily to satisfy new requirements. In this paper, we present our experience and results from four real-world deployments, each in a different context, of MVoice.		CE1	Não é da área da saúde.
071	A REST-based Framework to Support Non-Invasive and Early Coeliac Disease Diagnosis	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3345252.3345296	The health sector has traditionally been one of the early adopters of databases, from the most simple Electronic Health Record (formerly Computer-Based Patient Record) systems in use in general practice, hospitals and intensive care units to big data, multidata based systems used to support diagnosis and care decisions. In this paper we present a framework to support non-invasive and early diagnosis of coeliac disease. The proposed framework makes use of well-known technologies and techniques, both hardware and software, put together in a novel way. The main goals of our framework are: (1) providing users with a reliable and fast repository of a large amount of data; (2) to make such repository accessible by means of a suitable API in multiple modes, such as intuitive web-based or mobile visual interfaces; (3) to allow for data processing and analysis, as a basis for decision support systems.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
072	OpenMalaria and EMOD: a case study on model alignment	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.5555/2874916.2874952	This paper presents a case study of model alignment involving two independently developed agent-based malaria models. Each of these models simulates malaria transmission and various malaria interventions, such as insecticides, drugs, and bednets. EMOD specifically models both humans and mosquitoes as agents that interact with each other and interventions. However, OpenMalaria, only directly models humans as agents, while the mosquitoes interact based on results from several differential equations. This is the main difference between the two models, but there are several more, some which are not clearly noticeable without performing a complete comparison. In this docking exercise, we take a unique third-party perspective in order to determine equivalence between these two models. The successful alignment of OpenMalaria and EMOD further validates each model beyond their previous, individual validations. This case study also provides insight into the challenges and benefits of docking when none of the original model creators are fully involved in the exercise.		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.
073	Review of the Application of Blockchain Technology in Traditional Chinese Medicine Field	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3429889.3429932	The concept of blockchain has received a lot of attention and research since it was first proposed in 2008. With the popularization and development of blockchain technology, its huge development opportunities in the field of Traditional Chinese Medicine(TCM) have gradually revealed. This article studies the development path and technical characteristics of blockchain, analyzes the current research status of application of blockchain technology in medical field. It also summarizes the application and future research directions of blockchain technology in four typical TCM fields: TCM big data safe storage, Chinese medicine traceability, TCM electronic medical record privacy protection, TCM cloud health system and wearable devices. It is hoped that this paper can provide useful reference for relevant research.		CE5	Revisão da literatura.

074	Towards a deadline-based simulation experimentation framework using micro-services auto-scaling approach	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.5555/3400397.3400622	There is growing number of research efforts in developing auto-scaling algorithms and tools for cloud resources. Traditional performance metrics such as CPU, memory and bandwidth usage for scaling up or down resources are not sufficient for all applications. For example, modeling and simulation experimentation is usually expected to yield results within a specific timeframe. In order to achieve this often the quality of experiments is compromised either by restricting the parameter space to be explored or by limiting the number of replications required to give statistical confidence. In this paper, we present early stages of a deadline-based simulation experimentation framework using a micro-services auto-scaling approach. A case study of an agent-based simulation of a population physical activity behavior is used to demonstrate our framework.		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.
075	SIGS-S Mobile Saude: A Mobile Application to Support the Collection of Health Data	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.5555/2814058.2814159	The Brazilian government has asked for information systems to support government activities such as health care. Aiming to support the collection of health data in the context of the Health in The Family Program (Programa Saude na Familia) promoted by the Single Health System of Mato Grosso do Sul (Sistema Unico de Saude do Estado de Mato Grosso do Sul - SUS-MS), it was developed the mobile application SIGS-S Mobile Saude. The purpose of the mobile application is to provide the collection of health data in places where there is no internet connection using mobile devices such as tablets, providing the collected data to a web system called SIGS-S Web Saude via internet data transfer. A software process, named ProFap, was used to support the mobile application development. As a result, the mobile application was developed and its documentation was prepared to help future software maintenance and the deployment of SIGS-S Mobile Saude in the context of health care by SUS-MS. The application was developed and validated with participation of stakeholders consisting of health users and Brazilian government managers.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
076	Design a Secure Framework for Cloud-Based Medical Image Storage	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3090354.3090361	Actually, vast amounts of medical imaging data are created each year because healthcare professionals rely heavily on these digital records. Currently, healthcare industry still uses local data centers to store and manage patients' data. This concept causes a dramatic increase in operating expenses. To address this issue, medical providers are interested in implementing the cloud storage system. Indeed, the latter is meant to offer cost-efficient resources as a service through the Internet. Besides, clients are charged only based on cloud services utilization. Unfortunately, security and privacy are the main challenges for this new paradigm. This paper seeks to provide a deeper insight into existing implementations of cloud storage in the healthcare domain. Furthermore, we analyze and compare the current status of the cloud storage with security requirements. Accordingly, we design a secure framework to save medical image in a secure manner. To achieve this objective, segmentation and watermarking mechanisms are used to meet privacy requirements. In addition, the proposal uses multi-cloud environment as a storage system for attaining high security and performance.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
077	Benefits and required capabilities of BI-tools in the private healthcare	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3131085.3131128	Increasing amount of data in the healthcare sector requires specific tools that enable to process data in the rapidly changing environment. Especially in the private healthcare sector there is a clear need for appropriate tools to support decision-making process and thus, enhance profit making. Based on an empirical investigation of eight private healthcare sector organizations, we gain understanding on use of BI-tools in the private healthcare sector and utilization of them in decision-making. We analyse the capability factors and features of the BI-tools in the private healthcare industry sector, using the information systems (IS) success model by DeLone and McLean [1]		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema. Apresenta um estudo empírico.

			as our theoretical lenses for identifying the gained benefits and the success of BI-tool utilization.			
078	A dissemination-based mobile web application framework for juvenile idiopathic arthritis patients	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2492517.2500278	Adopting mobile technologies in assisting healthcare is opening new possibilities in medical health domain through bringing a dramatic shift from conventional paper-based tracking to electronic tracking and evaluation system. Health information systems have the potential to offer greater improvement in collecting and accessing relevant information, disseminating data among health practitioners and patients in a reliable and secure manner with faster speed and analyzing them efficiently. In this paper we have proposed and implemented a prototypical client-server based health information framework that allows both clinicians and patients to send data to a centralized backend system database and have access to those data when needed. Our framework adopts mobile electronic pain diary named PInGO for juvenile idiopathic arthritis patients to report their health conditions to the clinicians. Our framework offers secure, reliable and fast dissemination and access of these data through leveraging the latest push-based Web technology and RESTful web services. From our preliminary experiment results it has been observed that data dissemination using RESTful web services within event-based publish-subscribe domain provides greater performance improvement comparing to traditional pull-based data dissemination over Web.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
079	Priority-Based Resource Scheduling in Distributed Stream Processing Systems for Big Data Applications	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2492517.2500278	Distributed Stream Processing Systems (DSPSs) are attracting increasing industrial and academic interest as flexible tools to implement scalable and cost-effective on-line analytics applications over Big Data streams. Often hosted in private/public cloud deployment environments, DSPSs offer data stream processing services that transparently exploit the distributed computing resources made available to them at runtime. Given the volume of data of interest, possible (hard/soft) real-time processing requirements, and the time-variable characteristics of input data streams, it is very important for DSPSs to use smart and innovative scheduling techniques that allocate computing resources properly and avoid static over-provisioning. In this paper, we originally investigate the suitability of exploiting application-level indications about differentiated priorities of different stream processing tasks to enable application-specific DSPS resource scheduling, e.g., Capable of re-shaping processing resources in order to dynamically follow input data peaks of prioritized tasks, with no static over-provisioning. We originally propose a general and simple technique to design and implement priority-based resource scheduling in flow-graph-based DSPSs, by allowing application developers to augment DSPS graphs with priority metadata and by introducing an extensible set of priority schemas to be automatically handled by the extended DSPS. In addition, we show the effectiveness of our approach via its implementation and integration in our Quasit DSPS and through experimental evaluation of this prototype on a real-world stream processing application of Big Data vehicular traffic analysis.		CE1	Não é da área da saúde.
080	How android app developers manage power consumption?: an empirical	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2901739.2901748	As Android platform becomes more and more popular, a large amount of Android applications have been developed. When developers design and implement Android applications, power consumption management is an important factor to consider since it affects the usability of the applications. Thus, it is important to help developers adopt proper strategies to manage power consumption. Interestingly, today, there is a large number of Android application repositories made publicly available in sites such as GitHub. These repositories can be mined to help crystalize common power management activities that developers do. These in turn can be used		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.

	study by mining power management commits		to help other developers to perform similar tasks to improve their own Android applications. In this paper, we present an empirical study of power management commits in Android applications. Our study extends that of Moura <i>et al.</i> who perform an empirical study on energy aware commits; however they do not focus on Android applications and only a few of the commits that they study come from Android applications. Android applications are often different from other applications (e.g., those running on a server) due to the issue of limited battery life and the use of specialized APIs. As subjects of our empirical study, we obtain a list of open source Android applications from F-Droid and crawl their commits from Github. We get 468 power management commits after we filter the commits using a set of keywords and by performing manual analysis. These 468 power management commits are from 154 different Android applications and belong to 15 different application categories. Furthermore, we use open card sort to categorize these power management commits and we obtain 6 groups which correspond to different power management activities. Our study also reveals that for different kinds of Android application (e.g., <i>Games, Connectivity, Navigation, Internet, Phone & SMS, Time</i> , etc.), the dominant power management activities differ. For example, the percentage of power management commits belonging to <i>Power Adaptation</i> activity is larger for <i>Navigation</i> applications than those belonging to other categories.			
081	Improving data collection and monitoring through real-time data analysis	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2442882.2442916	Feedback based on real-time data is increasingly important for ICT-based interventions in the developing world. Applications such as facility inventories, summarization of patient data from community health workers, etc. need processes for analyzing and aggregating datasets that update over time. In order to facilitate such processes, we have created a modular web service for real-time data analysis: bamboo		CE1	Não é da área da saúde.
082	C4G BLIS: Health Care Delivery via Iterative Collaborative Design in Resource-constrained Settings	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2909609.2909657	Health care delivery in resource-constrained settings presents many challenges, including highly diverse workflows, lack of standardization in data collection and reporting, and scarcity along many dimensions such as infrastructure, income and education. Many attempts to introduce state-of-the-art standardized systems for electronic record keeping have met with limited success in these settings. We present the design, implementation and evaluation of C4G BLIS, a system that tracks patients, laboratory samples, test results, and generates customized reports and trends for patients, physicians and health officials. The system was designed and deployed based on two major principles: (1) an Iterative Cooperative Design (ICD) methodology (2) immediate and continuous benefits for day-to-day users of the system. C4G BLIS is currently in use in many large hospital laboratories in Africa, and we report on the experience and results from these deployments, including improved turn-around times, reduced error rates and user satisfaction.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
083	Re-Shape: A Method to Teach Data Ethics for Data Science Education	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3313831.3376251	Data has become central to the technologies and services that human-computer interaction (HCI) designers make, and the ethical use of data in and through these technologies should be given critical attention throughout the design process. However, there is little research on ethics education in computer science that explicitly addresses data ethics. We present and analyze Re-Shape, a method to teach students about the ethical implications of data collection and use. Re-Shape, as part of an educational environment, builds upon the idea of cultivating care and allows students to collect, process,		CE1	Não é da área da saúde.

			and visualize their physical movement data in ways that support critical reflection and coordinated classroom activities about data, data privacy, and human-centered systems for data science. We also use a case study of Re-Shape in an undergraduate computer science course to explore prospects and limitations of instructional designs and educational technology such as Re-Shape that leverage personal data to teach data ethics.			
084	FeatureNET: diversity-driven generation of deep learning models	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3377812.3382153	We present FeatureNET, an open-source Neural Architecture Search (NAS) tool ¹ that generates diverse sets of Deep Learning (DL) models. FeatureNET relies on a meta-model of deep neural networks, consisting of generic configurable entities. Then, it uses tools developed in the context of software product lines to generate diverse (maximize the differences between the generated) DL models. The models are translated to Keras and can be integrated into typical machine learning pipelines. FeatureNET allows researchers to generate seamlessly a large variety of models. Thereby, it helps choosing appropriate DL models and performing experiments with diverse models (mitigating potential threats to validity). As a NAS method, FeatureNET successfully generates models performing equally well with handcrafted models.		CE1	Não é da área da saúde.
085	Exploring security issues in telehealth systems	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1109/SEH.2019.00019	Telehealth systems (TS's) provide remote health-based services to improve the quality of service of patient treatment. Most healthcare professionals have access to standard telecommunications technology (such as Wireless Body Area Network (WBAN), biosensors, remote medical robots, and others) to offer remote care of elderly and physically less able patients as well as remote surgeries, treatments, and diagnoses. In order to ensure the functionality of TS's, several systemic properties must be satisfied, including security. Although there are studies that discuss different security approaches in TS's, it is difficult to have a clear view of existing security issues and solutions for these systems. In this article, a systematic mapping study was performed to detect, organize and characterize security issues in TS's. We identified 41 studies which were classified according to their research strategy, target problem, security issue addressed, and proposals. Results reveal that (i) 4 security issues were identified; (ii) 3 strategies were distinguished to handle security issues; (iii) patient and wireless medical data are the most affected medical supplies. Security in TS's reveals diverse challenges that concern Software Engineering. Areas such as requirements, software architecture, and security patterns play an important role in order to handle security issues.		CE5	Mapeamento sistemático da literatura.
086	Mined-Knowledge and Decision Support Services in Electronic Health	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1109/SDSOA.2007.9	Large organizations in various information domains are constantly facing the challenges of growing size, new business requirements, and customer demands for service agility. As an example, in the healthcare domain provision of unique electronic health record systems (EHR) for patient identification and health history, integration of regional systems into a nation-wide system, information and service sharing, and security and privacy of patient data have generated a set of new challenges. Canada Health Infoway has proposed an information infrastructure for networked healthcare systems that is based on service oriented architecture (SOA) and provides standards for sharing data and services. In this paper, we investigate the provision of mined-knowledge (results of data mining on patient data), clinical decision support systems, and network visualization and monitoring through SOA. We also address the advantages of SOA implementation using an enterprise service bus in order to accommodate these services. Such services can benefit similar domains such as banking, communications, air traffic control, and transportation.		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.

087	Evaluating domain-specific metric thresholds: an empirical study	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3194164.3194173	Software metrics and thresholds provide means to quantify several quality attributes of software systems. Indeed, they have been used in a wide variety of methods and tools for detecting different sorts of technical debts, such as code smells. Unfortunately, these methods and tools do not take into account characteristics of software domains, as the intrinsic complexity of geo-localization and scientific software systems or the simple protocols employed by messaging applications. Instead, they rely on generic thresholds that are derived from heterogeneous systems. Although derivation of reliable thresholds has long been a concern, we still lack empirical evidence about threshold variation across distinct software domains. To tackle this limitation, this paper investigates whether and how thresholds vary across domains by presenting a large-scale study on 3,107 software systems from 15 domains. We analyzed the derivation and distribution of thresholds based on 8 well-known source code metrics. As a result, we observed that software domain and size are relevant factors to be considered when building benchmarks for threshold derivation. Moreover, we also observed that domain-specific metric thresholds are more appropriated than generic ones for code smell detection.		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema. Apresenta um estudo empírico.
088	South-South Cooperation: Can Rwanda's Community Health Service Learn From Bangladesh's Info Lady	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2909609.2909619	This paper explores the opportunity of a cooperation and knowledge sharing among the two developing yet promising countries, Bangladesh and Rwanda. Using our own comparative framework and field research data, we critically analyze two specific ICT infused community health services in Bangladesh and Rwanda, and explore whether, under a common comparative framework, these two countries can learn from each other. We found that Rwanda has a top down approach with the government leading the implementations. On the other hand Bangladesh has a more inclusive approach with feedback loop among all the stakeholders. Such difference in the approach is reflected in three main aspects: service design, collaboration with partners and sustainability. We propose that sustainable entrepreneurship using health and related information as a commodity among the community health workers, supported by long term planning and strategic partnerships.		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.
089	Portinari: a data exploration tool to personalize cervical cancer screening	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2909609.2909619	Socio-technical systems play an important role in public health screening programs to prevent cancer. Cervical cancer incidence has significantly decreased in countries that developed systems for organized screening engaging medical practitioners, laboratories and patients. The system automatically identifies individuals at risk of developing the disease and invites them for a screening exam or a follow-up exam conducted by medical professionals. A <i>triage algorithm</i> in the system aims to reduce unnecessary screening exams for individuals at low-risk while detecting and treating individuals at high-risk. Despite the general success of screening, the triage algorithm is a one-size-fits all approach that is not personalized to a patient. This can easily be observed in historical data from screening exams. Often patients rely on personal factors to determine that they are either at high risk or not at risk at all and take action at their own discretion. Can exploring patient trajectories help hypothesize personal factors leading to their decisions? We present Portinari, a data exploration tool to query and visualize future trajectories of patients who have undergone a specific sequence of screening exams. The web-based tool contains (a) a visual query interface (b) a backend graph database of events in patients' lives (c) trajectory visualization using sankey diagrams. We use Portinari to explore diverse trajectories of patients following the Norwegian triage algorithm. The trajectories demonstrated variable degrees of		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.

			adherence to the triage algorithm and allowed epidemiologists to hypothesize about the possible causes.			
090	Workflow management for paramedical emergency operations within a mobile-static distributed environment	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/1645164.1645173	In this paper we present the OMU Workflow platform and underlying toolkit we developed based on the Triana Workflows environment, for implementing the Workflow Management of Paramedical Emergency Operations scenario within an intelligent context-aware mobile distributed Peer-to-Grid (P2G) infrastructure. The underlying OMU toolkit is a stand-alone system and the core components are independent of any workflow environment. We discuss the novel hybrid P2G architectural model we designed consolidating Peer-to-Peer and Grid computing research, providing new solutions to a dynamic distributed data-driven scenario that could radically increase the volume and timeliness of available information for decision support during the rescue operations. We also discuss the application of our workflow platform to other domain problems in our future work and the next steps in the path of testing and validation.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
091	A mobile point-of-care diagnostic system for low-resource settings	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2559206.2579415	Disease detection and epidemiology in developing countries are hampered by a lack of convenient, affordable and usable diagnostic technologies. The goal of this research project is to design, deploy and evaluate a mobile system that uses computer vision algorithms running on a mobile device to capture, interpret and transmit point-of-care diagnostic tests for infectious diseases. Our system will provide health workers around the world with access to rapid and accurate diagnoses for their patients and public health officials with real-time, aggregated data and statistics regarding the numbers and results of tests administered via a centralized database. Our system is currently being evaluated with sixty health workers at five clinical research sites in Zimbabwe. Our findings and insights could inform the design of future mobile health systems and help ministries of health and other stakeholders to assess the viability of deploying mobile systems in similar environments.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
092	Privacy and security in open and trusted health information systems	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.5555/1862795.1862802	The Open and Trusted Health Information Systems (OTHIS) Research Group has formed in response to the health sector's privacy and security requirements for contemporary Health Information Systems (HIS). Due to recent research developments in trusted computing concepts, it is now both timely and desirable to move electronic HIS towards privacy-aware and security-aware applications. We introduce the OTHIS architecture in this paper. This scheme proposes a feasible and sustainable solution to meeting real-world application security demands using commercial off-the-shelf systems and commodity hardware and software products.	CI1		
093	Research Challenges of Emerging Technologies Supporting Life-Long Health and Wellbeing	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3132635.3132639	In this article, we identify and discuss challenges imposed on technological research by emerging developments in health and wellbeing. We see an increasing importance of digital health literacy, the convergence of medicine and daily life, a shift from individual health to community care, a growth of personalized medicine, and the impact of internet of things on health. These developments mean challenges for technical research, such as the need, but also difficulties of interdisciplinarity, or the need to translate personal health data into medical information. Today's research approaches are not always best suited to deal with the challenges, e.g. of conducting real long term intervention studies, or taking into account regulatory issues. We propose a joint campaign by HCI, AI, UX and machine learning researchers, engineers, clinicians, regulatory bodies and all other interested parties in these subjects.		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.

094	Opportunities and challenges in connecting care recipients to the community health feedback loop	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3287098.3287111	This paper explores the design space of feedback systems that connect care recipients to the community health feedback loop. While related work in this vein has often emphasized gathering feedback for the sake of transparency alone, our study emphasizes opportunities to integrate the collection and use of feedback in ways that may improve the quality or equity of routine health services. We conducted a qualitative study using semi-structured interviews and focus groups with 23 participants in Kenya. Our field study makes current feedback practices visible; and reveals barriers faced by beneficiaries, community health workers, and their supervisors. Our findings identify relevant socio-technical complexities, and we outline concrete opportunities to design feedback systems that support and augment current practices. These contributions to the ICTD literature hold potential to inform the design of feedback systems that engage underserved populations in a systematic and equitable manner.		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema
095	Automatic detection of depression from text data: A systematic literature review	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3411564.3411603	Depression is a mental disorder that affects hundreds of millions of people worldwide, with potentially serious consequences if left without treatment. Despite that, many people still suffer from depression without a diagnosis. Recently, the amount of studies related to the automatic detection of depression has improved. The objective of this paper is to identify the methods and techniques used by studies about depression detection through text data, by conducting a systematic review.		CE4	Revisão sistemática da literatura
096	A Cost-Effective Method for Quality Assessment of Audiometric Bone Conduction Transducers	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.5555/3014393.3014399	This paper presents a cost-effective method for quality assessment of audiometric bone conduction transducers. Maximum hearing level, total harmonic distortion, and frequency response are measured for one medical-grade, and two consumer-grade products. Based on the proposed method, the experimental results show that one of the consumer-grade products can potentially be used to replace the compared medical-grade product.		CE1	Não é da área da saúde
097	Resolving data interoperability in ubiquitous health profile using semi-structured storage and processing	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3297280.3297354	Advancements in the field of healthcare information management have led to the development of a plethora of software, medical devices and standards. As a consequence, the rapid growth in quantity and quality of medical data has compounded the problem of heterogeneity; thereby decreasing the effectiveness and increasing the cost of diagnostics, treatment and follow-up. However, this problem can be resolved by using a semi-structured data storage and processing engine, which can extract semantic value from a large volume of patient data, produced by a variety of data sources, at variable rates and conforming to different abstraction levels. Going beyond the traditional relational model and by re-purposing state-of-the-art tools and technologies, we present, the Ubiquitous Health Profile (UHPr), which enables a semantic solution to the data interoperability problem, in the domain of healthcare1.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
098	Lessons from the deployment of the	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3123024.3125610	We report the design and deployment of a mobile health system for patients receiving primary care-based mental health services (Collaborative Care) for post-traumatic stress disorder and/or bipolar disorder in rural health centers. Here we describe the clinical model, our participatory approach to designing and deploying the mobile system, and describe the final system. We focus on the integration of the system into providers' clinical workflow and patient registry		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.

	SPIRIT app to support collaborative care for rural patients with complex psychiatric conditions		system. We present lessons learned about the technical and training requirements for integration into practice that can inform future efforts to incorporate health technologies to improve care for patients with psychiatric conditions.			
099	Microsimulation models for cost-effectiveness analysis: a review and introduction to CEAM	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.5555/3140065.3140097	In health policy and planning, decision-makers often need to consider the expected costs and population health outcomes of alternative choices. To aid in this effort, we developed a generalized microsimulation framework for estimating the cost-effectiveness of health interventions. We began by evaluating 18 existing microsimulation frameworks, including options based on the R programming language (e.g. msm, MicSim), Python (e.g. Liam-2, MIST) and standalone software (e.g. TreeAge, AnyLogic). We developed "hello, world" models in several frameworks and assessed them on computation speed, ease of use, and other criteria. This led us to develop a new framework in Python: a discrete-time Markov model called Cost-Effectiveness Analysis with Microsimulation (CEAM). In this paper, we present results from the review and demonstrate how to build a simple simulation with CEAM.		CEI	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
100	Advanced decision logic in simulation of material flow processing networks	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.5555/1162708.1162946	Material flow processing networks are ubiquitous in modern society. Such networks embody uncertainty, advanced decision logic, and increased performance expectations. As such, they have been subject to analysis by a variety of methods, with one of the most prominent being discreteevent simulation. Simulation enables detailed flow modeling, incorporates uncertainty and allows experiment-based performance assessment. Traditional approaches to simulation are not well-suited to modeling advanced decision logic, though. This paper explores the issue of representing advanced decision logic and presents a reference model for material flow processing networks to support such representations. Implementation issues are discussed, as well.		CEI	Não é da área da saúde.
101	A Human-in-the-Loop Cyber-Physical Approach for Students Performance Assessment	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3313294.3313387	As the number of smart devices that surround us increases, so do the possibilities of leveraging them to create intelligent, socially-aware systems. However, apart from e-health systems, few applications consider humans as active system players. In fact, most applications/systems have the sole objective of providing some service to humans without considering their intents, actions or emotions. In this respect, they can be looked at as open loop. Systems that do consider human feedback are called Human-in-the-Loop Cyber-Physical-Systems (HiTLCPS), and integrate the humans in a feedback loop, with potential to react and change the environment. In this paper, we propose an approach that implements the HITLCPS concept. The developed platform, ISABELA, explores both online social networks (OSN) data as well as a variety of other data, including environment data and data from personal mobile devices, thus combining IoT, social sensors and mobile sensing. In addition to present the system architecture, the paper provides preliminary results obtained during field trials.		CEI	Não é da área da saúde.
102	Fundamental requirements and DEVS approach for	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.5555/3213227.3213231	Systems of Systems (SoS) that include intelligence and adaptability exhibit high complexity that cannot be easily tackled using classic system engineering techniques. Recent model-based system engineering has also proved inadequate due to lack of a full-strength modeling and simulation (M&S) computational substrate. Such full-strength M&S support can help systems engineers to develop models of complex adaptive SoS that support design and testing of		CEI	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.

	modeling and simulation of complex adaptive system of systems: healthcare reform		mechanisms to coordinate component interactions and enable such mechanisms to improve over time. Successful application of this paradigm entails non-trivial pre-conditions to be put in place. In this paper, we discuss some of the requirements in the context of healthcare systems reform and an approach using formal Discrete Event Systems (DEVS) specification.			
103	Towards a Blockchain based Fall Prediction Model for Aged Care	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3290688.3290736	Falls are one of the major health concerns for the elderly people. These falls often result in severe injuries which lead into huge medical expenses. Over the recent years, many ICT based fall detection and fall prevention solutions emerged to address the risk factors associated with falls. However, despite of these research studies, predicting the likelihood of falls still remains as a huge challenge in both medical and IT research domains. Data related to these risk factors being scattered among different healthcare providers can be attributed as a main reason for this challenge. This is further amplified by healthcare providers being reluctant to disseminate the data beyond their entities due to the security and privacy concerns. However, in recent years, blockchain has been proven as a promising technology to address the security and privacy challenges in healthcare data exchange as it provides a shared, immutable, and transparent audit trail for accessing data. Therefore, in this paper, we are going to propose a conceptual blockchain based fall prediction model leveraging smart contracts and FHIR (Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources) standard to identify the elderly people who are at a higher risk of falling.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
104	Portable antenatal ultrasound platform for village midwives	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/1926180.1926209	Ultrasound imaging is an effective tool for identifying maternal mortality risk factors. Unfortunately, ultrasound is nearly absent in many rural healthcare facilities in developing regions due to the high costs of both equipment and required training. To leverage existing healthcare systems commonly found in these contexts, we have focused our efforts on increasing the diagnostic capabilities of midwives -- often central medical figures in rural and low-income communities. We have designed and built a low-cost portable ultrasound device consisting of a USB ultrasound probe and a touchscreen netbook for a total cost of around USD3500. Compared to currently available ultrasound devices, we simplified the user interface while maintaining functionality to allow midwives to detect three common obstetrical conditions: placenta previa, multiple gestations, and breech presentation. To evaluate our solution, we tested the accuracy of ultrasound measurements, image quality, and whether midwives could use ultrasound. Testing performed by nine clinicians indicated our device would be appropriate for identifying the three conditions. Our modular design approach allows for easy modification, and the device is designed to utilize existing local healthcare resources in order to create a sustainable solution that does not depend on continuous foreign assistance.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
105	Pragmatic interoperability for ehealth systems: the fallback workflow patterns	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3290688.3290736	Despite decades of research and development on interoperability standards, semantic interoperability among electronic health (eHealth) systems has largely remained an elusive goal. Interoperability functionality that has been implemented as part of national or provincial initiatives often ends up being considered unreliable in practice. We believe that a stronger focus on <i>workflows</i> and other <i>pragmatic</i> aspects of interoperability functions may be a key to overcoming these difficulties. Specifically, we argue that eHealth system interoperability should be modelled as dynamically evolving <i>socio-technical</i> processes, rather than as technical functions		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.

			of certified devices. In this paper, we explore the example of <i>patient referrals</i> to highlight common problems with eHealth system interoperability. We define a system-theoretic model of the socio-technical e-referral system to derive two pragmatic interoperability workflow patterns to address these problems. The presented research is carried out in collaboration with industry.			
106	The Sonzogno digital library project	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.5555/2655780.2655919	This poster reports on a work-in progress project of building a digital library for metadata records of books published by Sonzogno between 1800 and 1943. Metadata records from seven major libraries that have Sonzogno collections were harvested and used for building a unified collection for this project. Omeka, open-source software for building digital libraries, was used to host, manage, and provide the public with access to the collection. Currently, a sample set of the metadata of books published in 1885 is available from the digital library (http://sonzogno.cci.fsu.edu/). This poster reports on the current status of the project, explaining the process and challenges associated with building a digital library of the metadata collection (metadata harvesting and crosswalk) using Omeka.		CE4	Pôster.
107	Standardized representations and markup languages for multimodal interaction	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3233795.3233806	No abstract available.		CE4	Livro.
108	Computational operations research exchange (core): a cyber-infrastructure for analytics	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.5555/3400397.3400676	cORE is a new cyber-infrastructure which will facilitate computational Operations Research exchange. OR models arise in many engineering domains, such as design, manufacturing, and services (e.g., banking/finance, health systems), as well as specific infrastructure-centric applications such as logistics/supply chains, power system operations, telecommunications, traffic/ transportation, and many more. In addition, modern OR tools have also been adopted in many foundational disciplines, such as computer science, machine learning, and others. Given the broad footprint of OR, the development of a robust cyber-infrastructure has the potential to not only promote greater exchange of data, models, software, and experiments but also enhance reproducibility and re-usability, both within OR, and across multiple disciplines mentioned above. cORE also has the potential to drastically reduce the computational burden on research communities which study resource allocation using analytics. This paper presents an overview of the functionality, design, and computations using cORE.		CE1	Não é da área da saúde.
109	Improving community health worker performance through automated SMS	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2160673.2160677	Community health workers (CHWs) have been shown to be an effective and powerful intervention for improving community health. Routine visits, for example, can lower maternal and neonatal mortality rates. Despite these benefits, many challenges, including supervision and support, make CHW programs difficult to maintain. An increasing number of mHealth projects are providing CHWs with mobile phones to support their work, which opens up opportunities for real-time supervision of the program. Taking advantage of this potential, we evaluated the impact of SMS reminders to improve the promptness of routine CHW visits, first in a pilot study in Dodoma, Tanzania, followed by two larger studies with 87 CHWs in Dar es Salaam, Tanzania. The first Dar es Salaam study evaluated an escalating reminder system that sent SMS reminders directly to the CHW before notifying the CHW's supervisor after several overdue days. The reminders resulted in an 86% reduction in the average		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.

			number of days a CHW's clients were overdue (9.7 to 1.4 days), with only a small number of cases ever escalating to the supervisor. However, when the step of escalating to the supervisor was removed in the second study, CHW performance significantly decreased.			
110	Maternal Complications: Nuances in Mobile Interventions for Maternal Health in Urban Pakistan	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3136560.3136573	We present a three-phase exploration of mobile messaging to address the high rate of maternal mortality in low-income, urban Pakistan, with a focus on identifying deviations from previously published findings about mobile interventions in developing-world health. Phase 1 was a qualitative study of healthcare staff and pregnant mothers. It found that while the deeper medical challenges of maternal mortality were beyond the reach of ICT interventions, many of the problems could be partially addressed through a mobile-phone system that issued health-related information and reminders. In Phase 2, we ran a randomized controlled trial of 180 pregnant mothers split into four arms based on the mode by which the messages were sent -- (1) no messages (control), (2) SMS text messages, (3) recorded voice messages, and (4) a combination of SMS and voice messages. Consistent with prior research, we found that mothers receiving messages exhibited dramatic gains in knowledge about pre-natal care, though whether the messages increased follow-up hospital visits was not clear. Phase 3 involved follow-up phone interviews with the participants of the Phase 2 evaluation. Complex family dynamics involving husbands and mothers-in-law mediate the impact of mobile information interventions, with both positive and negative effects.		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.
111	A Real-Time IVR Platform for Community Radio	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2858036.2858585	Interactive Voice Response (IVR) platforms have been widely deployed in resource-limited settings. These systems tend to afford asynchronous push interactions, and within the context of health, provide medication reminders, descriptions of symptoms and tips on self-management. Here, we present the development of an IVR system for resource-limited settings that enables real-time, synchronous interaction. Inspired by community radio, and calls for health systems that are truly local, we developed "Sehat ki Vaani". Sehat ki Vaani is a real-time IVR platform that enables hosting and participation in radio chat shows on community-led topics. We deployed Sehat ki Vaani with two communities in North India on topics related to the management of Type 2 diabetes and maternal health. Our deployments highlight the potential for synchronous IVR systems to offer community connection and localised sharing of experience, while also highlighting the complexity of producing, hosting and participating in radio shows in real time through IVR. We discuss the relative strengths and weaknesses of synchronous IVR systems, and highlight lessons learnt for interaction design in this area.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
112	Supporting Maternal Health Education in Developing Countries Using Mobile Phones-Results of a Pilot Study	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2998581.2998588	With the high penetration of mobile technology in developing countries, researchers have started initiatives to fight maternal mortality with mobile phones and have indeed shown progress. However there is room for more research since maternal mortality is still high in developing countries. Moreover, most initiatives focus on helping health workers to improve service delivery, leaving room for research on how to engage mothers. We therefore propose a system prototype that supports pre-natal and postnatal healthcare by involving the women. Semi-structured interviews and questionnaires were used to collect data which was used to generate user and system requirements for the system. Based on the requirements, SMS gateways were evaluated to identify a suitable base for developing the system. The system was evaluated via usability and functionality testing. Results indicate that the implementation may be a feasible way to extend maternal health education to women and to reduce maternal mortality in the long run.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.

113	Towards a Digital Ecosystem for Predictive Healthcare Analytics	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2668260.2668286	Healthcare applications depend on voluminous data containing rich and important insights that can support predictive analysis by discovering these patterns using machine learning algorithms. Unfortunately this data is not always available for multiple reasons including lack of unified and standardized architecture for distribution / dissipation of such data. In this paper, we propose a framework for cloud based architecture of a digital ecosystem for storing, sharing and predictive analysis of healthcare data. We address the requirement for such a system and provide the design and architecture of the framework comprising of various interconnecting components. The proposed framework provides a cost effective digital ecosystem for collaboration, sharing and integration of Electronic Health Record systems by leveraging the benefits of cloud computing technologies. The framework provides a platform for various health care institutes, research organizations and government agencies to log data, develop predictive analytics models and collaborate in future research. A proof-of concept of the framework is implemented.	CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
114	Artificial neural networks applications in computer aided diagnosis: system design and use as an educational tool	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3012430.3012670	This paper describes the motivation, state-of-the-art, hypotheses and research objectives of the Doctoral Thesis " <i>Artificial Neural Networks applications in Computer Aided Diagnosis. System design and use as an educational tool</i> ". A description of the investigation approaches and methodologies, the current dissertation status and expected contributions is also presented. At the time of writing, this dissertation is in its first year of development. Its central topic is Computer Aided Diagnosis and Detection (CAD), a valuable automated tool for specialists who interpret medical images, that provides information which can be used as a "second opinion" or supplementary data in their decision making process. Developing CAD schemes based in the machine learning models called Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs), which could be applied to different image modalities, is the main objective of the first phase of the dissertation. Their integration in a software environment that allows the user to handle and access to information efficiently is of key importance in the process. The validation of the system in clinical practice and the investigation of their possible uses as an educational tool for trainees during residency programs is the second phase.	CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.
115	Enabling intelligent processes in simulation utilizing the TensorFlow deep learning resources	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.5555/3320516.3320655	Availability of large data sets and increased computing performance have contributed to many improvements in productivity and decision-making. Simulation can exploit these by incorporating data mining capabilities, such as machine learning, in the modeling and analysis process. This paper demonstrates the integration of discrete event simulation with a deep learning resource, known as TensorFlow, to enable intelligent decision making in the form of smart processes. A bank credit approval process is modeled using these smart processes to evaluate customer credit worthiness based on 20 reported features. Comparison of three models is made where credit worthiness is (1) known, (2) randomly assigned, or (3) evaluated based on customer features. Additionally, the experiment compares results under conditions where the process is perturbed by an unexpected surge in customer arrivals. The presented models and results demonstrate the feasibility of enabling smart processes in discrete event simulation software and the improved decision-making fidelity.	CE1	Não é da área da saúde.
116	Old, Sick And No Health Insurance.:	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3064857.3079127	We posit that as aging populations grow, so too will the demand for wearable devices that help people manage their chronic health conditions autonomously, at home, without medical supervision. Although healthcare providers are now integrating wearables into frontline services, the regulatory journey from consumer use to patient use for these devices is complex and oft protracted due to	CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.

	Will You Need A Permit To Use Your Home-made Health Wearable?		strict legislation. Through the creation of a design fiction -- HealthBand -- we explore how open source and crowd-funded wearables might impact future health product legislation. We argue that the generated artefacts co-construct a world in which HealthBand could plausibly exist, and in turn can help audiences engage more explicitly with the fiction's broader debates. Further, if future health wearables are to be adopted, HCI and design researchers must not focus solely on creating prototypes but also engage with regulatory change. We assert design fictions that build worlds like HealthBand have a role in highlighting the changes required.			
117	Remote Monitoring Applying IoT to Improve Control of Medication Adherence in Geriatric Patients with a complex Treatment Regimen, Lima-Peru	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3429536.3429543	Health care has changed profoundly thanks to the continuous improvement of electronic devices, recent rapid progress in wireless communications and microsystems has allowed the opportunity to automatically collect reliable patient data, yet communication about medication management through Transitions of care can be challenging, when older patients are treated for multiple health conditions in a nursing home. In this document, we propose an innovative architecture that employs Wireless Sensor Network (WSN) technologies with the NodeMCU which is an open source IoT (internet of things) platform and the Raspberry pi 3B+ that is used as an Mqtt server, for a smart pill dispenser, which will promote medication adherence, improve patient / user self-management; also assist in the efficient administration of therapies by reminding and registering medications for patients with a complex treatment regimen.	CI1		
118	Responsive Online Book based on the Multimedia Learning Theory	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.5555/2762722.2762737	The growing popularity of mobile devices with internet access has created a unique opportunity for exploitation by Distance Learning. To develop educational content for mobile devices is necessary to pay close attention to the technical aspects involved in educational interfaces. In this paper a mobile educational object developed by UNASUS/UFMA is presented: the responsive online book. The conception of its interface is based on the Multimedia Learning Theory and development standards for Responsive Web Design.		CE1	Não é da área da saúde.
119	Multimodal dialogue processing for machine translation	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3233795.3233811	No abstract available.		CE4	Livro.
120	Global Goods Software for the Immunization Cold Chain	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3378393.3402278	This paper explores the challenge of taking Global Goods software to international scale. Global Goods software is non-commercial software designed to support global development goals. We argue that a fundamental challenge behind this type of software is the different roles of the global organizations that fund projects, the country leadership that controls implementation, and the actual users of the software. To address this, it necessary to have a design process that balances interests of stakeholders and a technical design that allows for modularity and extensibility. We present a case study of an application for country level management of the immunization cold chain that we have developed and contrast it with major Global Goods software systems such as DHIS2 and OpenMRS. The contributions of the work include the design of a pipeline for building a Global Goods application that is deployed across multiple countries, a collection of lessons learned during system design and implementation, and a comparison of extensibility strategies of different global goods applications.		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.

121	<p>A big data architecture to a multiple purpose in healthcare surveillance: the Brazilian syphilis case</p>	<p>https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3401895.3402092</p>	<p>For many decades society did need to monitor and assess the standard of living of the population. In the 1950s, the United Nations (UN) saw this need and proposed 12 areas that should be evaluated, the first of which is listed under "Health and Demography", which focuses on what is expressed as the level of a population's health. Decades have passed and great results have been gained from similar initiatives such as reducing mortality from infectious diseases and even eradicating some others. In the age of the digital society, needs have grown. Monitoring demands that once perished from data to become concrete now suffer from the opposite effect, the excess of data from everywhere. Healthcare systems around the world use many different information systems, collecting and generating hundreds of data at unimaginable speed. We are billions of people on the planet and most of us are connected to the virtual world, sharing information, experiences and events with some kind of cloud. In this information age, the ability to aggregate and process this data is a major factor in raising public health to a new level. The development of tools capable of analyzing a large volume of data in seconds and producing knowledge for targeted decision making can help in the fight against specific diseases, in the process of continuing education of professionals, in the formation of new professionals, in the elaboration of new policies. with the specific locoregional look, in the analysis of hidden trends in front of so much information faced in everyday life and other possibilities. The present work proposes an architecture capable of storing and manipulating seeking to standardize the variables in order to allow to correlate this large amount of data in a systematic way, providing to several services and researchers the possibility of consuming health, social, economic and educational data for the promotion of public health.</p>	CE1	<p>Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.</p>
122	<p>Advanced migraine prediction simulation system</p>	<p>https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.5555/3140065.3140089</p>	<p>In the Internet of Things (IoT) era, there is growing interest in wireless monitoring sensors for detection, classification and prediction of health symptoms. The prediction of symptoms in chronic diseases such as migraines brings new hope to improve patients' lives. The prediction of a migraine symptomatic event through monitoring hemodynamic variables has been previously demonstrated in our earlier work. In this paper, a simulation-based approach for a real-time migraine prediction system is described. The simulation has been implemented using the specifications of the formal description language Discrete Event Systems (DEVS). The simulation system is a proof of concept that is ready for testing in a real-world ambulatory monitoring environment. The results obtained encourage developing a hardware/software (HW/SW) co-simulation system that incorporates Hardware-in-the-Loop (HIL) components as prior step to the expensive and slow hardware implementation of a complete migraine prediction device. When such a system is used in a real-time setting, it can simulate failures in sensors and trigger alarms for active patient response.</p>	CE1	<p>Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.</p>
123	<p>Seven factors for designing successful mHealth projects</p>	<p>https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2382856.2382865</p>	<p>Although mobile technology has the power to vastly improve healthcare delivery in developing regions, many issues can affect the success of mHealth systems.</p>	CE1	<p>Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.</p>
124	<p>A wireless system for monitoring</p>	<p>https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3401895.3402092</p>	<p>Arrhythmia is one of the most difficult problems in Cardiology and especially in Pediatric Cardiology. In this study, we present a mobile health (m-Health) system that will be used for continuous monitoring of children with suspected cardiac arrhythmias. The system is able to do real-time acquisition and transmission of ECG signals, and</p>	CE1	<p>Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.</p>

	of children with suspected cardiac arrhythmias	45/1579114.1579166	facilitate an alarm scheme able to identify possible arrhythmias so as to notify the on-call doctor and the relatives of the child that an event or something that denotes malfunction is happening. In general the problem has been divided into two cases. The first one, called "In-house case" the subject is located in his/her house. While for the second, called "Moving patient case" the subject might be located anywhere else. Our goal is the continuous 24 hours monitoring of the child. During the "In house case", a sensor network installed in the child's house will be used in order to continuously monitor ECG signals from the patient as well as environmental parameters. The second case is more general. For this case, the child will be monitored using the same ECG recording device but the signals will be transmitted, through a PDA device, directly to the central monitoring system. The transmission is performed through the use of 2.5G and 3G mobile communication networks. The system design, development and technical tests (using simulator) are finished. The next step will be the better verification of the system on healthy volunteers so as to get ready for application on patients.			
125	Modeling human behavior: an (ID)entity crisis?	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.5555/2693848.2694045	Agent-based modeling (ABM) has gained great popularity in recent years, especially in application areas where human behavior is important, because it opens up the possibility of capturing such behavior in great detail. Hybrid models which combine ABM with discrete-event simulation (DES) are particularly appealing in service industry applications. However in this paper we argue that many of the so-called distinctions between agents in an ABM and entities in a DES are artificial, and we describe several DES models which use standard entities to represent agent-like behaviors.		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.
126	ExerciseCheck: a scalable platform for remote physical therapy deployed as a hybrid desktop and web application	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3316782.3321537	ExerciseCheck is a scalable, accessible platform designed and developed for the remote monitoring and evaluation of physical therapy. Physical rehabilitation is an important aspect of a patient's recovery from injury and often requires the patient to perform a prescribed set of exercises over medium- to long-term periods. In the absence of a physical therapist, using a low-cost, non-intrusive solution can serve as a complement to in-clinic sessions and provide patients with valuable insights into their exercises. We present the design, implementation, and deployment of ExerciseCheck, a modular system that incorporates machine learning techniques with contemporary web technologies to enable a user-friendly experience for patients and physical therapists. Initially a proof-of-concept, the latest version of ExerciseCheck is now deployed as a hybrid desktop and web application at a Boston University rehabilitation clinic and has been employed by physical therapists in their sessions with individuals with Parkinson's disease. We provide insights into the usability requirements, architecture design, and implementation challenges of the development and deployment of a production-quality platform for remote physical therapy in a clinical setting.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
127	Simulating SKU proliferation in a health care supply chain	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.5555/1995456.1995779	This paper investigates stock keeping unit (SKU) proliferation and its impact on a health care supply chain. There are two types of proliferation: acceptance and adoption. The acceptance case occurs when a hospital requests a SKU and the SKU is not carried by the system. The adoption case occurs when the SKU is not carried by the requesting hospital, but is carried by some other hospital within the system. A multi-item, multi-echelon supply chain model with load building and delivery details was constructed to examine cost and performance tradeoffs. Object-oriented modeling and implementation techniques for the SKU proliferation simulation are described. The results indicate that the acceptance and adoption jointly affect the performance of the supply chain in terms of the service level (demand fill rate) and the cost. The models and results provide a test		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.

			bed for addressing and mitigating the effect of proliferation within healthcare supply chains.			
128	Automated System Health and Performance Benchmarking Platform: High Performance Computing Test Harness with Jenkins	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3155105.3155106	Datacenters have a growing need to monitor and maintain complicated computing machines and verify their systems are functioning at a high level. In order to achieve this goal, it is critical that administrators are able to readily verify basic user operations and survey system performance, quickly discerning when a configuration is sub-optimal. We have created a system health and performance monitoring tool that enables tracking both health and historical performance. The tool presents this data visually and enables the identification of realized and potential problems intuitively. This tool leverages Slurm, a workload manager common in, yet critical to High Performance Computing workflows. We construct the tool around Jenkins, a popular and well-supported testing automation framework which has been used in recent system health and regression testing, as well as PyTest, an assertion-driven Python unit test framework, after evaluating several potential automation tools and testing frameworks. This project develops a test harness for the Texas Advanced Computing Center to run multiple extendable suites of benchmarking and system health applications demonstrated on the Stampede2 and Lonestar5 HPC systems. The applications chosen to run within the test harness include existing in-house benchmarks, such as the Performance Assessment Workbench, and community benchmarks, e.g. STREAM, in addition to newly created system health monitoring scripts.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-abierto.
129	A tutorial on cloud computing for agent-based modeling & simulation with repast	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.5555/2693848.2693884	Cloud computing facilitates access to elastic high performance computing without the associated high cost. Agent-based Modeling & Simulation (ABMS) is being used across many scientific disciplines to study complex adaptive systems. Repast Symphony (Recursive Porous Agent Simulation Toolkit) is a widely used ABMS system. Cloud computing can speed-up significantly ABMS to facilitate more accurate and faster results, timely experimentation, and optimization. However, the many different Clouds, Cloud middleware and Service approaches make the development of Cloud-based ABMS highly complex. This tutorial introduces the CloudSME Simulation Platform (CSSP) that enables simulation software to be deployed as service (SaaS) supported by a cloud platform (PaaS). It shows how Repast can be deployed as a cloud computing service as part of a workflow of tasks. A case study demonstrates how the CSSP can easily run agent-based simulations written in Repast on multiple Clouds.		CE1	Não é da área da saúde. Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.
130	The Handbook of Multimodal-Multisensor Interfaces: Language Processing, Software, Commercialization, and Emerging Directions July 2019	https://dl.acm.org/doi/book/10.1145/3233795	No abstract available		CE4	Livro

131	Characterizing and mitigating work time inflation in task parallel programs	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.5555/2388996.2389085	Task parallelism raises the level of abstraction in shared memory parallel programming to simplify the development of complex applications. However, task parallel applications can exhibit poor performance due to thread idleness, scheduling overheads, and <i>work time inflation</i> -- additional time spent by threads in a multithreaded computation beyond the time required to perform the same work in a sequential computation. We identify the contributions of each factor to lost efficiency in various task parallel OpenMP applications and diagnose the causes of work time inflation in those applications. Increased data access latency can cause significant work time inflation in NUMA systems. Our locality framework for task parallel OpenMP programs mitigates this cause of work time inflation. Our extensions to the Qthreads library demonstrate that locality-aware scheduling can improve performance up to 3X compared to the Intel OpenMP task scheduler.		CE1	Não é da área da saúde.
132	SIGGRAPH '18: ACM SIGGRAPH 2018 Talks	https://dl.acm.org/doi/proceedings/10.1145/3214745	No abstract available.		CE4	Conferência.
133	TickTockRay Demo: Smartwatch Raycasting for Mobile HMDs	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2983310.2989206	We demonstrate TickTockRay, an implementation of fixed-origin raycasting technique that utilizes a smartwatch as an input device. We show that a smartwatch-based raycasting is a good alternative to a head-rotation-controlled cursor or a specialized input device. TickTockRay implements fixed-origin raycasting with the ray originating from a fixed point, located, roughly, in the user's chest. The control-display (C/D) ratio of TickTockRay technique is set to 1, with exact correspondence between the ray and the smartwatch's rotation. Such C/D ratio enables a user to select targets in the entire virtual reality control space.		CE1	Não é da área da saúde.
134	Early integration for movement modeling in latent spaces	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3233795.3233805	No abstract available.		CE4	Livro.
135	Data integration for mobile wellness apps to support treatment of GDM	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2843043.2843382	Data collected through mobile wellness apps is not currently effectively captured for clinical data use. It may be helpful to share data from wellness apps collected by the patients with clinicians. This study focuses on women with gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM). It is suggested that the team of clinicians taking care of these women could benefit if wellness data such as food diaries, exercise and glucose readings maintained in various mobile apps and blood glucose meters, are integrated using a software system into a format semantically interoperable with other health information systems (HIS). Potential clinical standards are explored in this work to be able to propose a possible solution for this interoperability.		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.
136	Supporting physicians by RE4S: evaluating	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.5555/2820158.2820166	Sustainable development applied to software engineering means developing systems in a sustainable way (domain-independent), as well as supporting sustainability in the application domain (domain-dependent). Developing sustainable software begins with requirements engineering (RE). RE for sustainability (RE4S) outlines the process of RE while taking steps to make the system more		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.

	requirements engineering for sustainability in the medical domain		sustainable. This approach answers the question, "What should this software system do, while contributing to overall sustainability?" This paper considers how sustainability impacts the requirements engineering process for a software system for medication adherence. The examined system, Project Cognatio, is targeted toward outpatient medical practices with the goal to improve medication adherence among patients. We found considering the dimensions of sustainability can significantly enrich a number of RE artifacts and thereby inform system's design. This analysis proves useful for the future development of Project Cognatio and shows that RE4S can improve software development's contribution to sustainability.			Realiza análise de requisitos.
137	MobileHelper: remote guiding using smart mobile devices, hand gestures and augmented reality	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2543651.2543664	Due to the rapid development in wearable computing, gestural interaction and augmented reality in recent years, remote collaboration has been seen as a fast growing field with many advanced designs and implementations for a wide range of applications. Most of existing remote guiding or collaboration solutions still rely on specifically designed hardware systems on both helper and worker side with limitations on usage, mobility, flexibility and portability. Considering widespread deployment of smart mobile devices such as smartphones and tablets in the past a few years, it already provides us numerous potentials of migrating conventional remote guiding solutions to such powerful platforms with the possibility of overcoming many existing issues and limits. In this paper, we introduce <i>MobileHelper</i> , a remote guiding prototype that is developed on a tablet device with the feature of allowing helpers to use hand gestures to guide the remote worker for various physical tasks. The interface used on the worker side integrates a near eye display to support mobility and real time representations of the helper's hand gestures using augmented reality technologies. We present the design and features of <i>MobileHelper</i> along with the description of detailed implementation of the prototype system. Stable system performance is also reported from our preliminary internal test runs.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
138	Privacy in the age of information (and algorithms)	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3331076.3331089	This paper raises the privacy issues related to information that is accessible about individuals from their mobile devices and that which is collected when they interact with and use so called "free" services provided on the web. The importance of privacy has been ignored by most legislation and any laws passed have no teeth. The only exception is the privacy protection that is embedded in the EU's General Data Protection Regulation(GDPR). GDPR gives control to individuals over their personal data and requires any organization which collects and controls personal information to have in place appropriate measures both technical and logistic, to implement the data protection principles. In this paper, we propose a technical solution to provide a personal email and web server with complete control of all correspondence and contents. This would liberate users from fake free services and provide privacy and security.		CE1	Não é da área da saúde
139	Harnessing Evolution of Multi-Turn Conversations for Effective Answer Retrieval	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3343413.3377968	With the improvements in speech recognition and voice generation technologies over the last years, a lot of companies have sought to develop conversation understanding systems that run on mobile phones or smart home devices through natural language interfaces. Conversational assistants, such as Google Assistant and Microsoft Cortana, can help users to complete various types of tasks. This requires an accurate understanding of the user's information need as the conversation evolves into multiple turns. Finding relevant context in a conversation's history is challenging because of the complexity of natural language and the evolution of a user's information need. In this work, we present an extensive analysis of language, relevance, dependency of user utterances in a multi-turn information-seeking conversation. To this aim, we have annotated relevant utterances in		CE1	Não é da área da saúde. Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.

			the conversations released by the TREC CaST 2019 track. The annotation labels determine which of the previous utterances in a conversation can be used to improve the current one. Furthermore, we propose a neural utterance relevance model based on BERT fine-tuning, outperforming competitive baselines. We study and compare the performance of multiple retrieval models, utilizing different strategies to incorporate the user's context. The experimental results on both classification and retrieval tasks show that our proposed approach can effectively identify and incorporate the conversation context. We show that processing the current utterance using the predicted relevant utterance leads to a 38% relative improvement in terms of nDCG@20. Finally, to foster research in this area, we have released the dataset of the annotations.			
140	Chronic Care Continuum (C³): mobile-ready life skills training for adolescents with chronic diseases	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2064942.2064954	Consensus guidelines from the American Academy of Pediatrics, American Academy of Family Physicians, and American College of Physicians recommend that physicians begin discussing the process of transitioning from pediatric to adult care with patients around age 12. Still, 59% of youth with chronic illness do not meet the core milestones for transitioning from pediatric to adult care. Challenges educating this population include patients experiencing apathy or denial, feelings of invincibility, and complex social factors that produce an environment not conducive to learning. The goal of Chronic Care Continuum (C ³ or "c-cubed") is to provide disease-specific educational content to each patient in their own environment. We aim to motivate at-risk patients to become more involved in their transition process through gaming techniques, incentives and rewards. C ³ suggests activities that patients perform in real life, building skills that they will need before assuming full responsibility for managing their disease. These skills include treatment adherence, nutritional awareness, social skills (e.g. talking to doctors), and self-monitoring for disease complications. Success at each activity is rewarded with points that can be converted to badges and privileges such as coaching other patients or unlocking games. We are specifically developing activities that can be performed using SMS-text, including taking pictures of healthy meals, reporting blood glucose levels, and competing with other users of the site in a trivia challenge. We will demonstrate C ³ for type 1 diabetes mellitus via videos of the interface working on an iPhone and the web site http://c3diabetes-t1.appspot.com .		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
141	Efficiency of electronic public service delivery in India: public-private partnership as a critical factor	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/1328057.1328133	The dynamics of public administration in India have altered drastically with the introduction of e-governance as a guiding concept in the late 1980s. Citizens, the world over, have been demanding smaller, effective and responsive governments, obviously inspired by the unprecedented and rapid success of finance capital in the global market. Consequently, policy makers began the search for smaller and efficient governments. On an evolutionary plane, reengineering of service systems, performance management, transparency in government operations, down sizing or right sizing the government workforce, emphasis on delivery of reliable public services and ultimately citizen satisfaction came to be considered as benchmarks by most of the administrators. Quick decision-making, data-based planning, effective implementation through quantitative techniques seemed to have clinched the issue. This reformative pattern was no different in the Indian context, where the governments at the federal and state levels were in search of new techniques and technologies. Information technology has been found to be very useful in reinvigorating the government administrative systems by enhancing their capacity and efficiency. The potential and scope for application of IT in governing processes and transactions are enormous. E-government can transform traditional administrative		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.

			<p>systems through employment of information and communication technologies. A governance system that is committed to working with civil society, and by extension, private industry in a transparent and accountable way to reduce poverty, redress imbalances in access to resources, foster security and uphold social, economic, cultural, civil and political rights is the ultimate objective of e-governance theory. In practice, much depends on the collaboration patterns that the governments seek to establish. E-governance practices in India emerged and evolved mainly from native intuition, but under prescription for lesser and transparent government by international financial institutions, mainly the World Bank and the International Monetary Fund. However, the range of success of e-governance initiatives has not been uniform. The bottom-up demand for delivery of electronic services was bleak initially, but the change in public perception was for the better with the governments roping in private industry and service-oriented organizations gradually. The Public-Private Partnership (PPP) model as is construed normally in a world that is fast witnessing globalization of all businesses and administrative trends, especially in the realm of e-governance, involves features such lesser government investment in electronic delivery of public services, collaboration in conceptualizing, designing and implementing the e-governance projects besides increased participation of stakeholders -- both private and public -- to saturate the levels and the reach of such projects. India is no exception to the general rule dictating PPP mode in e-governance. The unprecedented success of the PPP modules in e-governance in India can be rightly established with two path-breaking e-governance models - e-Seva in the state of Andhra Pradesh and Bhoomi in Karnataka. These projects not only caused a jump in revenue collections of the two state governments, but also timely payment by the citizens. Time and costs for availing public services have come down drastically bringing in a positive change in peoples' perception of e-governance theory and practice. This holds equally true for both the rural and urban populace. The result of all these radical changes in public administration systems is the enhanced satisfaction level of the citizenry on delivery of public services and simplification of governmental procedures. The above mentioned e-government projects can serve as models for all the developing societies.</p>			
142	<p>Digital healthcare in Latin America: the case of Brazil and Mexico</p>	<p>https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3423923</p>	<p>No abstract available</p>		CE4	Revista
143	<p>CrossZig: combating cross-technology interference in low-power wireless networks</p>	<p>https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.5555/2959355.2959365</p>	<p>Low-power wireless devices suffer notoriously from Cross-Technology Interference (CTI). To enable co-existence, researchers have proposed a variety of interference mitigation strategies. Existing solutions, however, are designed to work with the limitations of currently available radio chips. In this paper, we investigate how to exploit physical layer properties of 802.15.4 signals to better address CTI. We present CrossZig, a cross-layer solution that takes advantage of physical layer information and processing to improve low-power communication under CTI. To this end, CrossZig utilizes physical layer information to detect presence of CTI in a corrupted packet and to apply an adaptive packet recovery which incorporates a novel cross-layer based packet merging and an adaptive FEC coding. We implement a prototype of</p>		CE1	Não é aplicado em saúde.

			CrossZig for the low-power IEEE 802.15.4 in a software-defined radio platform. We show the adaptability and the performance gain of CrossZig through experimental evaluation considering both micro-benchmarking and system performance under various interference patterns. Our results demonstrate that CrossZig can achieve a high accuracy in error localization (94.3% accuracy) and interference type identification (less than 5% error rate for SINR ranges below 3 dB). Moreover, our system shows consistent performance improvements under interference from various interfering technologies.			
144	DORIC: An Architecture for Data-intensive Real-time Applications	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3229345.3229416	This study presents Doric, a software architecture for data-intensive real-time applications. Dimensions of data-intensive real-time applications are introduced, as well as technologies that enable the implementation of such dimensions. A case study involving a portable electroencephalogram (EEG) enabled data collection based on realistic scenarios found in data-intensive real-time applications. The Doric architecture was implemented using recent technologies (e.g., Apache Kafka) for building real-time data pipelines and streaming applications. This prototype was evaluated in five scenarios containing different volumes of data. The obtained results were encouraging and show the potential for applying Doric as a structure to foster the development of modern information systems in organizations and to support serve as a guideline for new corporate architectures.	CI1		
145	Intelligent Computing for Interactive System Design: Statistics, Digital Signal Processing, and Machine Learning in Practice	https://dl.acm.org/doi/book/10.1145/3447404	No abstract available.		CE4	Livro.
146	A low-cost flexible IoT system supporting elderly's healthcare in rural villages	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3283458.3283470	We propose to create a system that, by exploiting the possibilities provided by the Internet of Things (IoT), offers a cheap and affordable solution to prevent and control health problems of people, especially elderly, living in rural villages, where assessing good health facilities is a major concern. The system consists of a heterogeneous combination of apps and Arduino-based devices that connect patients and healthcare service providers remotely located. An important feature from the interaction point of view is that the system is easily configurable by non-technical people, e.g., caregivers.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
147	Cybersecurity Indexes for eHealth	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3290688.3290721	This study aimed to explore the cybersecurity landscape to identify cybersecurity indexes that may be relevant to the health industry. While the healthcare sector poses security concerns regarding patients' records, cybersecurity in the healthcare sector has not been given much consideration. Cybersecurity indexes are a survey that measures security preparedness and capabilities of a country or organisation. An index is made up of a series of questions, often broken into categories. These categories target areas such as law, technical responses, organisational threats, capacity building and social context. Some indexes provide ranking capabilities against		CE5	Survey.

			<p>other countries, while others directly evaluate what it means to be cyber-ready. In this paper, cybersecurity indexes were reviewed regarding the level of assessment (country level/organisation level), and their consideration of the wider community, the health sector, and their appearance in academic literature. Results from this study found that there was no consistency between the indexes investigated, with each index having a diverse number of categories and indicators. Some indexes resulted in a score; others did not rank their results in league tables. Evidence to calculate the level of adherence was often obtained from secondary sources, with four of the country indexes using both primary and secondary sources. Eight (out of fourteen) indexes measured wider community indicators and only one index specifically measured eHealth services. Findings from the initial systematic review suggest that hardly any peer-reviewed journal articles exist on the topic of cybersecurity indexes. The paper concludes that most of the indexes studied are broad and do not consider the eHealth sector specifically. Each index relies on a different process to gauge cybersecurity, with little to no academic rigour. It is expected that this research will contribute to the current (limited) literature addressing cybersecurity indexes.</p>			
148	<p>Systematically Understanding the Cyber Attack Business: A Survey</p>	<p>https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3199674</p>	<p>Cyber attacks are increasingly menacing businesses. Based on the literature review and publicly available reports, this article conducts an extensive and consistent survey of the services used by the cybercrime business, organized using the value chain perspective, to understand cyber attack in a systematic way. Understanding the specialization, commercialization, and cooperation for cyber attacks helps us to identify 24 key value-added activities and their relations. These can be offered “as a service” for use in a cyber attack. This framework helps to understand the cybercriminal service ecosystem and hacking innovations. Finally, a few examples are provided showing how this framework can help to build a more cyber immune system, like targeting cybercrime control-points and assigning defense responsibilities to encourage collaboration.</p>		CE5	Survey.
149	<p>Low-Cost Mobile Learning Solutions for Community Health Workers</p>	<p>https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3041021.3053377</p>	<p>Accredited Social Health Activists in India play a critical role in improving the access to healthcare services of rural populations. Despite their key contribution in Millennium Development Goals, they receive inadequate training and supervision. Traditional face to face training face challenges of infrastructure, management and cost. Existing research studies have highlighted the potential of alternative approaches e.g. mHealth for capacity building, however so far they mainly focus on providing job aids only. In this thesis, we are exploring mobile technologies for building a distance learning platform for ASHAs; which is low cost, feasible and relevant to the local context. We propose our system that combines Internet and IVR technology in a novel way such that it allows the trainers to connect to ASHAs through a conference call and host structured real time interactions via a smartphone application. To evaluate the system we have conducted a field deployment of four weeks in the Haryana state, India. In collaboration with an NGO we provided a training intervention to 20 ASHAs on Home Based Newborn Care and found positive outcomes in terms of learning gains and acceptability by the stakeholders. We aim to build a comprehensive mobile learning solution that utilizes the available resources efficiently in order to produce larger impact.</p>		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
150	<p>Distributed hybrid agent-based discrete</p>	<p>https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.5555/2675983.2676186</p>	<p>This paper presents the development of a distributed hybrid agent-based (ABS) discrete event simulation (DES) model within the context of emergency medical services (EMS). The existing simulation models of EMS either are considered as a single model or several standalone models that represent different system elements in isolation. The aim of this research is to demonstrate the feasibility of</p>		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.

	event emergency medical services simulation		using distributed simulation technology to implement hybrid EMS simulation. This would provide opportunities to study holistically integrated improvement scenarios for emergency medical services and crisis management systems. The case study is based on the London EMS and consists of an ambulance service ABS model and several accident and emergency departments DES models. Both the ABS and the DES models were developed in Repast Simphony toolkit using poRTico RTI software to achieve communication between them. The results prove that we can use distributed simulation to successfully represent the real system.			
151	Experiences in mHealth for chronic disease management in 4 countries	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2093698.2093868	This paper describes mHealth applications to deal with Non Communicable Diseases in North and Latin America: In Chile, a project focused on Diabetes Mellitus type 2; In the United States, Honduras, and Mexico, projects focused in diabetes, heart failure, depression, hypertension, and cancer. Information Technologies used include voice and sms on cell phones and electronic health records systems.		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.
152	Semantic relatedness study using second order co-occurrence vectors computed from biomedical corpora, UMLS and WordNet	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2110363.2110405	Automated measures of semantic relatedness are important for effectively processing medical data for a variety of tasks such as information retrieval and natural language processing. In this paper, we present a context vector approach that can compute the semantic relatedness between any pair of concepts in the Unified Medical Language System (UMLS). Our approach has been developed on a corpus of inpatient clinical reports. We use 430 pairs of clinical concepts manually rated for semantic relatedness as the reference standard. The experiments demonstrate that incorporating a combination of the UMLS and WordNet definitions can improve the semantic relatedness. The paper also shows that second order co-occurrence vector measure is a more effective approach than path-based methods for semantic relatedness.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
153	Reducing Incarceration through Prioritized Interventions	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3209811.3209869	The most vulnerable individuals in society often struggle with long-lasting, multi-faceted challenges like mental illness, substance abuse, chronic health conditions, and homelessness. Individuals experiencing these difficulties tend to interact with public services and departments frequently, but many communities are struggling to identify those individuals, let alone meet their needs in meaningful and cost-effective ways. In this paper, we describe our work with Johnson County, Kansas, that uses machine learning to prioritize outreach to individuals most at risk of being booked into jail within the next year. For the first time, we brought together Johnson County's jail, emergency medical, and mental health data, identified individuals who touch multiple systems, and built a model to predict individual jail bookings. Our system significantly outperformed both a random baseline and several simple heuristics that domain experts are likely to use and implement. By focusing on 200 individuals (which is the intervention capacity of Johnson County) who had interacted with both mental health services and the criminal justice system, we predicted jail bookings in the following year with 51% precision, which outperforms a baseline heuristic model by 1.5 times, and is 4.6 times better than a random baseline. This work provides a framework and prototype system for Johnson County as well as many other jurisdictions that are part of the Data Driven Justice Initiative as they develop intervention models to proactively connect social and mental health workers with individuals in need of care to avoid incarceration.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.

154	Learning Management Systems as Platforms for Increasing the Digital and Health Literacy	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3355166.3355176	Today, information and communication technology (ICT), that covers a wide plethora of various software applications and hardware devices, plays role as an integrated part and routine of the everyday lives, hence rapidly changing the manner of approaching to the useful information. In order to function effectively in the contemporary digital society, individuals need appropriate skills to be digitally literate and these skills need to be updated for information evaluation and knowledge gathering. Beside these digital literacy skills, another skills covering the ability to obtain, read, understand, and use healthcare information for addressing or solving various health problems are needed. In order to increase these both skills between population, especially between people with disabilities and elderly people, easiest way is to provide e-learning courses. Choosing the appropriate learning management system (LMS) in accordance with the Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) standard in order to increase the digital and health literacy is a challenging task. In this paper we analyze and compare the key differences of the 8 most commonly used LMSs, according to the WCAG standard predefined criteria.		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.
155	Annotating with light for remote guidance	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/1324892.1324911	This paper presents a system that will support a remote guidance collaboration, in which a local expert guides a remotely located assistant to perform physical, three-dimensional tasks. The system supports this remote guidance by allowing the expert to annotate, point at and draw upon objects in the remote location using a pen and tablet-based interface to control a laser projection device. The specific design criteria for this system are drawn from a tele-health scenario involving remote medical examination of patients and the paper presents the software architecture and implementation details of the associated hardware. In particular, the algorithm for aligning the representation of the laser projection over the video display of the remote scene is described. Early evaluations by medical specialists are presented, the usability of the system in laboratory experiments is discussed and ideas for future developments are outlined.	CI2		
156	Lessons learnt from the participatory design of a mobile care data application in a resource-restricted context	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2348144.2348184	This case describes the participatory process of developing a mobile solution for care givers in a resource-restricted context. The experiences of the designers and developers during this process are shared. mHealth solutions are not yet widely adopted for care giving services and the lessons learnt could be valuable to others designing similar solutions. The literacy level of the care givers as end-users was an important consideration for selecting the right methods to involve them in the design of the solution. It was a challenge to design the solution for the kind of mobile phones used by the care givers in these poorer communities since these phones have limited functionality. The design of the mobile solution as well as the process to involve the end-users were therefore influenced by the constraints of the context of use.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
157	UICDS compliant resource management system for emergency response	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.5555/1809874.1809882	The essential components of effective emergency management and response include pertinent information sharing across various government agencies as well as non-governmental and private organizations to assess the situation, identify the needed resources for emergency response and generate response plans. Interoperability is a key requirement for information sharing from disparate systems and organizations, such as the case in emergency response. In this paper, we present a emergency response system that comprises of the following component: (1) ontology library for resolving the semantic differences of information pertaining to the incident, its severity, resource requirements and resource availability; (2) reasoning engine		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.

			for deriving the resource requirements and emergency response plans based on the policies of different agencies and modes of cooperation; (3) workflow management for visualization, status monitoring, execution, and adaptation of emergency response process; and (4) a geographical interface for visualization of situational awareness data. Utilizing the recent initiative by the Department of Homeland Security (DHS) Science and Technology division to architect, develop, and deploy a standards-based information sharing infrastructure called UICDS (Unified Incident Command and Decision Support), our system enables effective information sharing and interoperability among different New Jersey state agency systems. These include the RDDB of the NJ Office of Emergency Management (NJOEM), Hippocrates of the New Jersey Department of Health and Senior Services (NJDHSS), the special person's registry of the NJ state.			
158	Exploring schema repositories with schemr	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2007206.2007210	Schemr is a search engine for users to search for and visualize schemas in a metadata repository. Users may search by keywords and by example, using schema fragments as query terms. Schemr uses a novel search algorithm, based on a combination of text search and schema matching techniques, coupled with a structurally-aware scoring metric. Schemr presents search results in a GUI that allows users to explore which elements match and how well they do. The GUI supports interactions, including panning, zooming, layout and drilling-in. This paper introduces Schemr as a new component of the information integration toolbox and discusses its benefits in several applications.		CE1	Não é da área da saúde.
159	A technological infrastructure design for a pediatric oncology network	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/1579114.1579151	In Italy, the service of Pediatric oncology is very centralized and granted by high-specialized medical structures. In particular, in the Italian Regione Campania there are just few of such medical centers that, in case of room availability, take care of the child from the diagnosis until his/her complete healing, providing all necessary treatments along with a number of assistance services both for the patient and his parents. Regione Campania centers are often congested, causing a migration of more than 35% of the young patients towards extraterritorial centers. Also, these medical centers are often far away from the place where the patients leave, forcing them to have recurrently long traveling, sometimes just for a routine test. However, in the Regione Campania there are a lot of facilities and hospitals with high technology equipments and qualified staff that, by means of an appropriate network organization based on a computer network infrastructure, could help during the children's protocol treatment and thus significantly contribute to improve the local and national pediatric oncology service. This paper reports an evaluation research for the development, through an engineering approach based on a "hub and spoke" model, of a complete and efficient information system that allows the organization and sharing, at different levels, of clinical information among high-specialized medical centers and the other entities.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
160	Open science: approaches and benefits for modeling & simulation	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.5555/3242181.3242220	Open Science is the practice of making scientific research accessible to all. It promotes open access to the artefacts of research, the software, data, results and the scientific articles in which they appear, so that others can validate, use and collaborate. Open Science is also being mandated by many funding bodies. The concept of Open Science is new to many Modelling & Simulation (M&S) researchers. To introduce Open Science to our field, this paper unpacks Open Science to understand some of its approaches and benefits. Good practice in the reporting of simulation studies is discussed and the Strengthening the Reporting of Empirical Simulation Studies (STRESS) standardized checklist approach is presented. A case study shows how Digital Object Identifiers, Researcher Registries, Open		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema

			Access Data Repositories and Scientific Gateways can support Open Science practices for M&S research. The article concludes with a set of guidelines for adopting Open Science for M&S.			
161	Explaining an increase in predicted risk for clinical alerts	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3368555.3384460	Much work aims to explain a model's prediction on a static input. We consider explanations in a temporal setting where a stateful dynamical model produces a sequence of risk estimates given an input at each time step. When the estimated risk increases, the goal of the explanation is to attribute the increase to a few relevant inputs from the past. While our formal setup and techniques are general, we carry out an in-depth case study in a clinical setting. The goal here is to alert a clinician when a patient's risk of deterioration rises. The clinician then has to decide whether to intervene and adjust the treatment. Given a potentially long sequence of new events since she last saw the patient, a concise explanation helps her to quickly triage the alert. We develop methods to lift static attribution techniques to the dynamical setting, where we identify and address challenges specific to dynamics. We then experimentally assess the utility of different explanations of clinical alerts through expert evaluation.		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.
162	Ada3D: Real-Time 3D Reconstruction with Compression Rate Adaptation	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3393527.3393544	Augmented reality, so called AR, is recently the subject of attention by researchers from different fields and is developing rapidly. However, some attractive AR applications do not have mature technical basis yet, such as holographic conference and telesurgery. In these applications, 3D reconstruction of the target objects and real-time transmission of the reconstructed result are needed. It is challenging to build an integrated real-time 3D reconstruction system and effectively reduce the transmission delay within the system. In this paper, we propose Ada3D, a practical cross-platform system for real-time 3D reconstruction using multiple RGB-D sensors. It consists of several sensory clients and an edge server, which are responsible for data acquisition and data fusion, respectively. In addition, a compression-based method is applied in the system, which enables the client to automatically select an appropriate data compression level according to the current system state, including network status and device capability. Experiment results show that the method outperforms the common case by over 10% in delay saving.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
163	Learning games for the cognitively impaired people	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2899475.2899487	Learning environments have been profoundly reshaped by pervasive technology. New educational methodologies take full advantage of ICT in a mobile customized user-friendly environment, to support learning and stimulate individuals' potential. Unfortunately, technology-enhanced learning tools are not often designed with accessibility in mind, although they can greatly benefit the personal empowerment and inclusion of special-needs people. To address this gap, a Web platform has been created for delivering accessible games to people with Down syndrome. Since personalization, orderliness and positive reinforcement are crucial to learning in these subjects, the platform offers a personalized safe environment for learning, conforming to behavioral analysis principles. Learning analytics are incorporated in the platform for easy monitoring of student progress via Web interfaces. The participatory design driving the development of the learning platform allowed the customization of the games' discriminative stimuli, difficulty levels and reinforcement, as well as the creation of a game "engine" to easily set up new personalized exercises. These customization features make the game platform usable by a larger audience, including individuals with learning difficulties and autism.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
164	Open and trusted	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.5555/1862758.1862774	Information and Communications Technologies globally are moving towards Service Oriented Architectures and Web Services. The healthcare environment is rapidly moving to the use of Service Oriented Architecture/Web Services systems interconnected via this		CI1	

	information systems/health informatics access control (OTHIS/HIAC)		global open Internet. Such moves present major challenges where these structures are not based on highly trusted operating systems. This paper argues the need of a radical re-think of access control in the contemporary healthcare environment in light of modern information system structures, legislative and regulatory requirements, and security operation demands in Health Information Systems. This paper proposes the Open and Trusted Health Information Systems (OTHIS), a viable solution including override capability to the provision of appropriate levels of secure access control for the protection of sensitive health data.			
165	Clinician Perspectives on the User Experience, Configuration, and Scope of Use of a Patient Reported Outcomes (PRO) Dashboard	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3329189.3329198	To improve care coordination, forestall emergencies, and save costs, there is a growing movement to have patients at home habitually collect and provide data about their health status and related experiences to health care providers. One aspect of this movement involves the recurring use of reliable and valid questionnaires to collect and share patient reported outcomes (PRO) data. However, studies indicate that health care providers have a host of legitimate concerns about the systematic and routine collection, sharing, and use of PRO data. To explore these provider-specific concerns further, we developed a configurable prototype software application for use by providers and their patients called the PRO Data Dashboard (PDD). Using the PDD along with several written clinical case scenarios, we conducted focus groups with a diverse group of oncology care providers to generate findings relevant to the design, configuration, and use of PRO-based tools. We organized our findings into three categories: scope of use of PRO tools, configuration of PRO tools, and clinician user experience. We conclude that providers require fine-grained control over the configuration of PRO data collection and sharing features in e-Health applications.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
166	Antibiotic-Responsive Bioart: Exploring DIYbio as a Design Studio Practice	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3173574.3174037	Our work links hybrid practices from biology, fine arts, and design in a studio setting to support materially-oriented engagement with biotechnology. Using autoethnographic methods, we present our two-year process of converting an HCI studio into a BSL-1 (biosafety level 1) facility, our iterative development of low-cost tools, and our own self-reflexive experimentation with (DIY)bio protocols. Insights from this work led us to design a weeklong bioart course, whereby junior highschool students creatively "painted" with bacteria and antibiotic substances, digitally designed stencils from the resulting petri dish images, and screenprinted them onto physical artifacts. Our findings reveal the nuances of working with biological, analog, and digital materials in a design studio setting. We conclude by reflecting on DIYbio studio as a gathering of diverse actors who work with hybrid materials to give physical form to matters of concern.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
167	Modularizing deep neural network-inspired recommendation algorithms	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3240323.3241618	This tutorial reviews recent developments of deep neural network-based recommendation algorithms and demonstrates how to extend and adapt such algorithms for diverse application scenarios. The customization is supported by OpenRec framework that modularizes neural recommenders. The tutorial consists of a lecture and two hands-on sessions. It targets intermediate and advanced audiences who already possess knowledge of deep neural networks and are interested in applying those knowledge to the domain of recommendation. Materials are available at: http://openrec.ai/		CE1	Não é da área da saúde.
168	MM '20: Proceedings of the 28th	https://dl.acm.org/doi/proceedings/10.1145/3394171	No abstract available		CE4	Conferência.

	ACM International Conference on Multimedia				
169	Toward Automated Evaluation of Empathetic Responses in Virtual Human Interaction Systems for Mental Health Scenarios	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3383652.3423916	This paper investigates the process of automating the evaluation of empathetic response levels in virtual human interaction systems implementing mental health scenarios. Two suicidal virtual patients were developed to collect clinician participants' empathetic responses. Before collecting clinicians' responses, we tested the virtual human interaction with healthcare trainees. Trainees' empathetic responses were evaluated by experts to use the ECCS scale based on the ECCS level (Empathetic Communication Coding System). We trained classifiers using trainees' empathetic responses with experts' coded empathy levels as the training dataset. Clinician participants' empathetic responses to virtual patients were evaluated by experts and the classifiers. The performance of the classifiers was evaluated using the experts' coded level of clinicians' empathetic responses as a test dataset. This work demonstrates the applicability of using virtual agents techniques to identify empathy levels of clinicians' responses automatically. This work shows the potential of using virtual human interaction to train clinicians' skills to show empathy. Corresponding feedback could be provided to clinicians based on the evaluation results. We hope this study motivates more research in using intelligent virtual agents in personal skills training in education.	CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
170	Strategies for Playful Design when Gamifying Rehabilitation: A Study on User Experience	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3056540.3056550	Gamifying rehabilitation is an efficient way to improve motivation and exercise frequency. However, between flow theory, self-determination theory or Bartle's player types there is much room for speculation regarding the mechanics required for successful gamification, which in turn leads to increased motivation. For our study, we selected a gamified solution for motion training (an exergame) where the playful design elements are extremely simple. The contribution is three-fold: we show best practices from the state of the art, present a study analyzing the effects of simple gamification mechanics on a quantitative and on a qualitative level and discuss strategies for playful design in therapeutic movement games.	CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema. Não é da área da saúde.
171	GigaTensor: scaling tensor analysis up by 100 times - algorithms and discoveries	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2339530.2339583	Many data are modeled as tensors, or multi dimensional arrays. Examples include the predicates (subject, verb, object) in knowledge bases, hyperlinks and anchor texts in the Web graphs, sensor streams (time, location, and type), social networks over time, and DBLP conference-author-keyword relations. Tensor decomposition is an important data mining tool with various applications including clustering, trend detection, and anomaly detection. However, current tensor decomposition algorithms are not scalable for large tensors with billions of sizes and hundreds millions of nonzeros: the largest tensor in the literature remains thousands of sizes and hundreds thousands of nonzeros. Consider a knowledge base tensor consisting of about 26 million noun-phrases. The intermediate data explosion problem, associated with naive implementations of tensor decomposition algorithms, would require the materialization and the storage of a matrix whose largest dimension would be $\approx 7 \times 10^{14}$; this amounts to ~ 10 Petabytes, or equivalently a few data centers worth of storage, thereby rendering the tensor analysis of this knowledge base, in the naive way, practically impossible. In this paper, we propose GIGATENSOR, a scalable distributed algorithm for large scale tensor decomposition. GIGATENSOR exploits the sparseness of the real world tensors, and avoids the intermediate data explosion	CE1	Não é da área da saúde.

			problem by carefully redesigning the tensor decomposition algorithm. Extensive experiments show that our proposed GIGATENSOR solves 100 times bigger problems than existing methods. Furthermore, we employ GIGATENSOR in order to analyze a very large real world, knowledge base tensor and present our astounding findings which include discovery of potential synonyms among millions of noun-phrases (e.g. the noun 'pollutant' and the noun-phrase 'greenhouse gases').			
172	Social media analytics and research test-bed (SMART dashboard)	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2789187.2789196	We developed a social media analytics and research testbed (SMART) dashboard for monitoring Twitter messages and tracking the diffusion of information in different cities. SMART dashboard is an online geo-targeted search and analytics tool, including an automatic data processing procedure to help researchers to 1) search tweets in different cities; 2) filter noise (such as removing redundant retweets and using machine learning methods to improve precision); 3) analyze social media data from a spatiotemporal perspective, and 4) visualize social media data in various ways (such as weekly and monthly trends, top URLs, top retweets, top mentions, or top hashtags). By monitoring social messages in geo-targeted cities, we hope that SMART dashboard can assist researchers investigate and monitor various topics, such as flu outbreaks, drug abuse, and Ebola epidemics at the municipal level.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
173	A systematic literature review on the description of software architectures for systems of systems	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2695664.2695795	Software architectures have been recognized as the backbone to the success of any software system. In addition, they are responsible to aggregate quality attributes, such as interoperability, dependability, and maintainability, to these systems. In parallel, currently, a new class of complex software systems has emerged, referred as Systems of Systems (SoS), resulting from a number of operationally and managerially independent software systems working together to fulfill a mission that none system alone could provide. Considering their complexity, the development of SoS has demanded special attention to their software architectures. In this scenario, the description of such architectures, i.e., the way that these architectures are represented/documentated, becomes quite important as it can improve communication as well as evaluation and maintenance of these architectures. Despite its relevance, there is still no complete panorama about architectural descriptions of SoS. The main contribution of this paper is to present results of a Systematic Literature Review (SLR) on how SoS software architectures have been described. As main result, there are already important contributions in that direction; however, there is a lack of consensus on how better dealing with these descriptions. We conclude this paper with directions on how a consensus could be achieved and which aspects of the SoS architectural descriptions require further investigation.		CE5	Revisão sistemática da literatura.
174	A mobile core-body temperature monitoring system on Android	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2221924.221954	Recently, Google launched the Android mobile operating system and several mobile devices already support it. This paper proposes a mobile Android-enabled tool for collecting, monitoring, and analyzing intra-vaginal temperature. A previous proposed intra-vaginal sensor acquires temperature values and sends the collected data to Android device over a Bluetooth connection. The Android tool allows women for real-time monitoring of their temperature with mobility support and following their daily life. Woman can control and detect their fertile and ovulation periods when this human parameter increases about 0.5°C over their regular temperature. Other application of this solution includes the preterm labor prevention. The proposed system was evaluated and validated, and it is ready for use.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.

175	Health Multimedia: Lifestyle Recommendations Based on Diverse Observations	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3078971.3080545	Managing health lays the core foundation to enabling quality life experiences. Modern multimedia research has enhanced the quality of experiences in fields such as entertainment, social media, and advertising; yet lags in the health domain. We are developing an approach to leverage multimedia systems for human health. Health is primarily a product of our everyday lifestyle actions, yet we have minimal health guidance on making everyday choices. Recommendations are the key to modern content consumption and decisions. Cybernetic navigation principles that integrate health media sources can power dynamic recommendations to dramatically improve our health decisions. Cybernetic components give real-time feedback on health status, while the navigational approach plots health trajectory. These two principles coalesce data to enable personalized, predictive, and precise health knowledge that can contextually disseminate the right actions to keep individuals on a path to wellness.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
176	QFuzz: quantitative fuzzing for side channels	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3460319.3464817	Side channels pose a significant threat to the confidentiality of software systems. Such vulnerabilities are challenging to detect and evaluate because they arise from non-functional properties of software such as execution times and require reasoning on multiple execution traces. Recently, noninterference notions have been adapted in static analysis, symbolic execution, and greybox fuzzing techniques. However, noninterference is a strict notion and may reject security even if the strength of information leaks are weak. A quantitative notion of security allows for the relaxation of noninterference and tolerates small (unavoidable) leaks. Despite progress in recent years, the existing quantitative approaches have scalability limitations in practice. In this work, we present QFuzz, a greybox fuzzing technique to quantitatively evaluate the strength of side channels with a focus on min entropy. Min entropy is a measure based on the number of distinguishable observations (partitions) to assess the resulting threat from an attacker who tries to compromise secrets in one try. We develop a novel greybox fuzzing equipped with two partitioning algorithms that try to maximize the number of distinguishable observations and the cost differences between them. We evaluate QFuzz on a large set of benchmarks from existing work and real-world libraries (with a total of 70 subjects). QFuzz compares favorably to three state-of-the-art detection techniques. QFuzz provides quantitative information about leaks beyond the capabilities of all three techniques. Crucially, we compare QFuzz to a state-of-the-art quantification tool and find that QFuzz significantly outperforms the tool in scalability while maintaining similar precision. Overall, we find that our approach scales well for real-world applications and provides useful information to evaluate resulting threats. Additionally, QFuzz identifies a zero-day side-channel vulnerability in a security critical Java library that has since been confirmed and fixed by the developers.		CE1	Não é da área da saúde.
177	A GIS-based serious game recommender for online physical therapy	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2676629.2676634	As human-centered interactive technologies, serious games are getting popularity in a variety of fields such as training simulations, health, national defense, and education. To build the best learning experience when designing a serious game, a system requires the integration of accurate spatio-temporal information. Also, there is an increasing need for intelligent medical technologies, which enable patients to live independently at home. This paper introduces a novel e-Health framework that leverages GIS-based serious games for people with disabilities. This framework consists of a spatial map-browsing environment augmented with our newly introduced multi-sensory Natural User Interface. We propose a comprehensive architecture that includes a sensory data manager, a storage layer, an information processing and computational intelligence layer, and a		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.

			<p>user interface layer. Detailed mathematical modeling as well as mapping methodology to convert different therapy-based hand-gestures into navigational movements within the serious game environment are also presented. Moreover, an Intelligent Game Recommender has been developed for generating optimized navigational routes based on therapeutic gestures. Motion data is stored in a repository throughout the different sessions for offline replaying and advanced analysis; and different indicators are displayed in a live manner. This framework has been tested with Nokia, Google maps, ESRI map, and other maps whereby a subject can visualize and browse the 2D and 3D map of the world through therapy-based gestures. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first GIS-based game re-commender framework for online physical therapy. The prototype has been deployed to a disability center. The obtained results and feedback from therapists and patients are very encouraging.</p>			
178	<p>Security in a smart city: challenges and solutions</p>	<p>https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3368756.3369076</p>	<p>In this paper we will discuss what concerns the smart city, the services in a smart city, also the mechanism of data processing and data analysis especially the data generated by the sensors because it considered a point of vulnerability in a smart city that's why we have to propose a smart solution system, it will be based on intrusion detection systems, this solution should be adapted with a smart environment. We choose Intrusion Detection Systems because they are presently getting to be one of the important issue for any association's system. Intruders scan for vulnerabilities or imperfections in the target system and attack using different techniques. An intrusion detection system is needed to detect malicious actions and respond to the objectives of security such as confidentiality, integrity. Today, many open sources and commercial Intrusion Detection Systems are available to match organization's requirements but the problem is how we can choose one of these solutions that are adaptable with a smart environment.</p>		CEI	<p>Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema. Não é da área da saúde.</p>
179	<p>Compressing and Filtering Medical Data in a Low Cost Health Monitoring System</p>	<p>https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3139367.3139382</p>	<p>Current work evaluates the precision of low-cost medical sensors, which are incorporated in an e-health platform presented recently by the authors. The sensors' accuracy is an important issue that is investigated in this paper in order to highlight the medical cases where the low-cost developed e-health platform can be used in a fairly reliable way. Specifically, the sensor values obtained from the e-health platform were filtered using the methods of moving average window (MAW), Principal component analysis (PCA) and simplified Kalman filter. It is shown that although moving average window achieves a significant error reduction, the produced output introduces a latency penalty in the original sensor signal. Kalman filter exhibits worse performance from both the MAW and the PCA methods. Finally, it is demonstrated that the PCA method sustains advanced compression of about 30% while in the same time reduces the error of the primary signal measurement, thus improving the sensor accuracy.</p>		CEI	<p>Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.</p>
180	<p>Improving healthcare using cognitive computing based software: an application</p>	<p>https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1007/978-3-642-31087-4_50</p>	<p>The goal of this paper is to define the platform specifications dealing with medical information sharing both from research viewpoint and in terms of local health care. The purpose of this research work is based on doctor - patient relationships: VDS - Virtual Medical Doctor System. At this stage the platform is only used for scientific purposes. In particular, we assume the integrated design of the platform based on different levels (layers), which may be interconnected through the information flows (or links). The first level (the lower) involves the construction of a VDS platform. Based on this system it is possible to foresee a number of extensions such as social network for scientific research design, and risk analysis tool.</p>		CEI	<p>Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.</p>

	in emergency situation					
181	The Handbook of Multimodal-Multisensor Interfaces: Signal Processing, Architectures, and Detection of Emotion and Cognition	https://dl.acm.org/doi/book/10.1145/3107990	The Handbook of Multimodal-Multisensor Interfaces provides the first authoritative resource on what has become the dominant paradigm for new computer interfaces: user input involving new media (speech, multi-touch, hand and body gestures, facial expressions, writing) embedded in multimodal-multisensor interfaces that often include biosignals. This edited collection is written by international experts and pioneers in the field. It provides a textbook, reference, and technology roadmap for professionals working in this and related areas. This second volume of the handbook begins with multimodal signal processing, architectures, and machine learning. It includes recent deep-learning approaches for processing multisensorial and multimodal user data and interaction, as well as context-sensitivity. A further highlight is processing of information about users' states and traits, an exciting emerging capability in next-generation user interfaces. These chapters discuss real-time multimodal analysis of emotion and social signals from various modalities and perception of affective expression by users. Further chapters discuss multimodal processing of cognitive state using behavioral and physiological signals to detect cognitive load, domain expertise, deception, and depression. This collection of chapters provides walk-through examples of system design and processing, information on tools and practical resources for developing and evaluating new systems, and terminology, and tutorial support for mastering this rapidly expanding field. In the final section of this volume, experts exchange views on the timely and controversial challenge topic of multimodal deep learning. The discussion focuses on how multimodal-multisensor interfaces are most likely to advance human performance during the next decade.		CE4	Livro.
182	Using patient data for personalized cancer treatments	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2581892	Patient information databases eventually will help improve health outcomes and support development of new therapies.		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.
183	Biometric access control for e-health records in pre-hospital care	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2457317.2457345	Efficient and privacy-preserved access to the health record of patients is necessary to correctly practice medicine. This research addresses two concerns in emerging health software systems. First, electronic health records are not yet remotely accessible without using a token (e.g. health card). Second, patients' privacy must be preserved even in special situations such as emergency cases. This paper proposes to exploit <i>biometric identification</i> to access a central health record database featured by <i>privacy policies</i> . The experiments implement a real world scenario in which an ambulance reaches an unconscious patient who needs pre-hospital medical care for which their health record is retrieved from the database and is modified to meet privacy policies. The results demonstrate an average response time of 19.8 seconds when over 200K patients are registered in the database.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
184	Including the Voice of Care Recipients in Community Health Feedback	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3359173	Community health programs in low-resource settings (like rural Kenya) aim to provide essential health services to vulnerable populations. However, to date, there has been limited research that explores the design of mechanisms that enable care recipients to provide feedback regarding their satisfaction with the services they receive. Such feedback has the potential to increase the motivation of community health workers (CHWs), enhance training procedures, detect fraudulent behavior, and inform key performance indicators for health programs. Our paper explores the design and deployment		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.

	Loops in Rural Kenya		of a USSD-based system that allows anyone who possesses a basic mobile phone to provide feedback regarding the health services and quality of care they received from a CHW or during a hospital visit. Our system was designed through iterative fieldwork in rural Kenya that engaged with multiple stakeholder groups, including care recipients, CHWs, and high-level decision makers. After designing and testing the system, we deployed it for seven weeks in Siaya, Kenya, collecting both quantitative system usage data and qualitative data from six focus groups with 42 participants. Findings from our deployment show that 168 care recipients engaged with the system, submitting 495 reports via USSD. We discuss the broader factors impacting deployment, including the feasibility of USSD, actionability of feedback, scalability, and sustainability. Taken together, our findings suggest that USSD is a promising approach for enabling care recipients to submit feedback in a way that balances privacy, equity, and sustainability.			
185	Multimodal conversational interaction with robots	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3233795.3233799	No abstract available		CE4	Livro
186	Integrating Blockchain Technology in Healthcare via Active Learning	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3374135.3385275	As the healthcare industries move into the digitalization of health records, blockchain application could be a significant game-changer in the healthcare sector, creating a secure and flexible ecosystem for the exchange of records. Making healthcare clearer by creating a blockchain system to eliminate fraud and improve data accuracy is vital. Blockchain can securely interoperable record data such as organs, blood, critical drugs, and keeping medical licenses and certificates. With the emergence of Bitcoin, the first popular blockchain decentralized application, blockchain has become a viable solution for recording transactions in a growing list called blocks which are linked and protected using cryptography. However, with the ever-increasing demand for blockchain professionals and developers, there are few hands-on labs/modules available for training current students, the future developer professionals. The objective is to develop a framework including a series of hands-on labs that would fit individual student's needs for blockchain in public health. This framework will help students to find their current level and propose an appropriate level of the hands-on lab for developing blockchain decentralized - applications in public health. This approach will help students to learn and comprehend the fundamental blockchain concepts systematically. A set of hands-on labs would be built based on real-life scenarios, to enhance their ability to understand and solve real-life cybersecurity problems in healthcare. This integrated approach would expose the students to the cost to risk involved at each stage of the blockchain application for electronic health records.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
187	AI in Global Health: The View from the Front Lines	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3411764.3445130	There has been growing interest in the application of AI for Social Good, motivated by scarce and unequal resources globally. We focus on the case of AI in frontline health, a Social Good domain that is increasingly a topic of significant attention. We offer a thematic discourse analysis of scientific and grey literature to identify prominent applications of AI in frontline health, motivations driving this work, stakeholders involved, and levels of engagement with the local context. We then uncover design considerations for these systems, drawing from data from three years of ethnographic fieldwork with women frontline health workers and women from marginalized communities in Delhi (India). Finally, we outline an		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.

			agenda for AI systems that target Social Good, drawing from literature on HCI4D, post-development critique, and transnational feminist theory. Our paper thus offers a critical and ethnographic perspective to inform the design of AI systems that target social impact.			
188	Whose participation? whose knowledge?: exploring PD in Tanzania-Zanzibar and Sweden	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/1147261.1147277	In this paper we discuss two Participatory Design (PD) projects, one in Tanzania-Zanzibar and the other one in Sweden. In both countries the design process was done through the analysis of work practices involving both designers and users. The discussion focuses on a number of factors such as location, time and scene. We also ask how different projects can be that it is still possible to talk about PD as an overall participation and design approach. If PD is not a singular, definite, closed and fixed approach on the explicit layers, so how do these projects relate to each other when focusing on methods embracing the ambiguities of participation? The paper ends with a discussion of differences and similarities considering participation in the projects.		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.
189	Prevention of Medication Loss through a Marketplace and Blockchain	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3376044.3376059	The emergence of a digital marketplace in the world and especially in Brazil around 2012 has innovated the way merchants and consumers use technology to commercialize products and services. Consumers are able to search for products and services from many merchants at once while merchants can reach consumers in many different platforms as well as creating a network of business and relationships between the two. This article demonstrates the results of a platform being developed that uses the concepts of a marketplace to prevent the loss of medications that are close to expiring. The solution was developed using a Java, Typescript and NodeJS platform for the consumers to interact with the marketplace using Hyperledger Fabric Blockchain framework, creating a low-cost and simple platform, preventing fraud and increasing flexibility, security and transparency.	CI1		
190	Big Data Technologies to Improve Medical Data Warehousing	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3090354.3090376	The purpose of this review is to explore how the use of big data technology improves the performance of medical data warehousing. Indeed, traditional data warehousing tools can no longer be used to handle the volume, variety, and velocity of today's data-centric medical applications. Moreover, Big data technologies can be used to process the streams of medical data, they increase performance by using a cluster of existing networked nodes through powerful processing of these streams. In this paper, we provide an overview of state-of-the-art research issues of data warehousing technologies in the medical field and the opportunities presented by big data technologies. Whereas, an appropriate use of the current technology of big data especially Hadoop could help to overcome issues of medical data warehousing.		CE5	Revisão da literatura.
191	Bridging a gap in the proposed personal health record	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/1183568.1183578	The emerging electronic health record infrastructure is guiding records to be stored in repositories that collectively supply a patient's comprehensive health history. However, legal and technological constraints may keep such a system from delivering health histories in a timely manner (i.e., when medical attention is needed). To get around this, we propose a design for a portable personal health record system that complies with HIPAA standards of security and interaction. The authenticity of stored records on this PHR is automatically verifiable, increasing its usefulness to health care providers. Our initial work suggests that it is possible to develop a useful, yet secure PHR.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
192	Voting advice applications: a successful	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2490257.2490263	Voting Advice Applications (VAAs) are web applications that enable voters to compare their political views with the positions of the political parties. VAAs have been used successfully in many West European countries for more than a decade, but most of the Balkan countries do not have an established VAA. The aim of this paper is to		CE1	Não é da área da saúde.

	nexus between informatics and political science		promote the use of VAAs by showing that these applications -- if they are built on high academic standards -- can become useful tools for all stakeholders: i) voters who become more knowledgeable about the positions of the parties and they can make better vote choices, ii) political parties that have the opportunity to make their views known to a part of the electorate that is not fully covered by traditional communications channels, and iii) VAA researchers who are able to gather a huge amount of data that can be used to study voters' electoral behavior.			
193	Participatory Design that Matters—Facing the Big Issues	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3152421	At a time where computer technology is putting human lives and work under pressure, we discuss how to provide alternatives. We look back at Participatory Design (PD) which was originally about possibilities and alternatives as much as it was about specific solutions. The paper aims to revitalize and revise PD to help people influence <i>big issues</i> . The agenda for this is set through proposing a set of key elements for realizing new, important possibilities. We discuss the possible changes of partnership with users, call for a new role of researchers as activists, debate how to work with demanding visions for lasting impact, and democratic control. We focus on high technological ambitions, on deployment of working prototypes, on alliances, and on scaling up, all seen as important for a PD that matters. We conclude the paper with an invitation to participate in the continued discussion, codesign, and realization of a PD that matters.		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema. Não é da área da saúde.
194	Botswana's Lab-In-A-Briefcase: A Position Paper	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3290688.3290716	Detecting and managing communicable and non-communicable diseases in rural settings of Africa raises numerous structural, syntactical and semantic issues. Further, it has been observed that both Communicable Diseases (CDs) such as TB and Non-Communicable Diseases (NCDs), such as cancer, diabetes, cardiovascular diseases and chronic respiratory disease, are on the rise in sub-Saharan African countries and estimated to account for about 25% of deaths (Bloomfield et al., 2014) [8]. In Botswana, NCDs account for more than a third of all deaths in the country (WHO NCD country profile, 2014) [9]. For cash-poor part of Africa, this additional spend-requirement in healthcare is unfortunately substantial. One approach to reducing death related to CD/NCD is early detection and control through data collection and appropriate intervention. In sub-Saharan Africa countries, most of the population lives in rural areas where access to healthcare facilities is very limited. In such circumstances, a low-cost and mobile healthcare facility along with associated Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) would be of great assistance. This paper investigates the application of the "lab-in-a-briefcase" technology for the management of CDs/NCDs in Botswana and other SADC countries. The "lab-in-a-briefcase" is designed to provide a portable laboratory diagnosis toolkit with rapid results (about 15 minutes) that can be used in areas where access to laboratory or healthcare facility is limited and can be used with minimal training. It contains all the necessary tools and chemicals/reagents which are packaged in a briefcase form so that they can easily be carried. In addition, the Lab-in-a-briefcase employs mini-HPLC and smart camera, microphone, credit card-sized ECG and microscope so that a variety of tests can be performed quickly and efficiently in a portable manner. This paper details the design and deployment of "Lab-in-a-briefcase" and associated software tools at primary care health facilities so that diagnosis can be quickly carried out and the resulting medical records are automatically generated, converted into appropriate format and securely shared with different health information systems. The deployment of this system requires adaptation of the system in the context of the linguistic, legal, security, and other policy requirements of the participating countries.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.

			As part of the demonstration of the applicability, pilot studies will be extended to all participating African countries. Our end-objective is to develop a fully optioned prototype.			
195	Building Wearables for Geology: An Operating System Approach	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2903267.2903275	Wearable devices have emerged in the last years with new applications that provide user convenience. Healthcare, sports, safety are some examples of applications embedded in thousands of devices released in the last years. Wearable operating systems with different focus emerged together with wearable applications in order to make adjustments and optimizations of software and hardware. This paper presents a wearable operating systems discussion and shows the current challenges and wearable operating system inuence. We developed a wearable appliance for geology. The wearable contains a Head Mounted Display (HMD) assembled with Google Cardboard API and sensors connected to developments boards. For each system component was used different operating systems according to hardware and software available. The results indicate some trends for wearable operating systems.		CE1	Não é da área da saúde.
196	A public health application of data analysis for homeland security	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.5555/1351542.1351748	This presentation follows up the talk last year to WINFORMS (The Washington Institute for Operations Research and The Management Sciences) in which an approach developed for the analysis of military command and control during crises was shown to be relevant to surveillance for an infectious disease outbreak. ProMEDMail is an Internet-based system dedicated to rapid global dissemination of information on outbreaks of infectious diseases and acute exposures to toxins that affect human health. The presentation will demonstrate how the collection, formatting, and analysis of raw data, using ProMED-Mail, can point to emerging biological incidents and allow the real-time dissemination of results to local, regional, and central health facilities.		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.
197	Male Partner Engagement in Family Planning SMS Conversations at Kenyan Health Clinics	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3209811.3209857	Maternal health outreach and engagement is a common goal of mobile health (mHealth) projects for development. Male partners of pregnant and postpartum women are known to be important influences on their health behavior. This paper presents a novel extension to previous HCI4D research by exploring how to engage male partners in SMS-based family planning conversations. First, we explore design considerations for inclusion of male partners in an existing semi-automated bidirectional SMS platform. A 12-month randomized controlled trial of a family planning counseling SMS program was conducted in western Kenya using our system. A total of 260 pregnant women and 101 of their male partners were enrolled in the system. We analyze enrollment and usage data from this trial to compare baseline technology use and demographics of mothers and their male partners. Our findings demonstrate significant technology gender divides in the study population. Finally, we explore how both the mothers and their male partners interacted with the SMS system through an analysis of over 11,500 messages. We conclude that it is feasible to include rural Kenyan men in an SMS-based family planning discussion program and that their inclusion does not dramatically affect the mothers' engagement.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
198	Smart city knowledge management: Holistic review and the analysis of the urban	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3396956.3398263	The purpose of this paper is to review city ecosystem systems interactions for urban knowledge management practices and prepare a theoretical discussion about the issues of digital resource management processes. It is going for a conceptual paper based on the literature review and smart city case studies around the world. This theoretical study helps to understand the smart city knowledge management process, and it is focusing on knowledge phenomenon from a holistic perspective, that include smart cities knowledge-based activities, urban data platforms, cyber-physical environment, smart (urban) technologies and city stakeholders. The paper consists of presentations about the smart city ecosystem, definition the smart		CE4	Revisão da literatura.

	knowledge management		city stakeholders and their role and the explanation of smart city knowledge management and its processes. The authors' holistic view facilitates some types of data collection methods of raw as well as processed data and of knowledge-based activities of different stakeholders. This text can serve as a strong background for scientific future			
199	BESI: reliable and heterogeneous sensing and intervention for in-home health applications	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1109/CHASE.2017.73	Advances in sensing, wireless communication, and data analytics have enabled various monitoring systems for smart health applications. However, many challenges remain to deploy such systems in actual homes, such as achieving robustness, unobtrusiveness, fault tolerance, privacy, and minimal user burden. This paper presents how these challenges were overcome in the realization and successful prototype deployment of the Behavioral and Environmental Sensing and Intervention (BESI) system. BESI is designed to sense behavioral activities using wearables and monitor environmental parameters with in-home sensors. With such data, behavioral patterns can then be modeled to determine associations with environmental attributes and, when appropriate, real-time notifications or interventions can be made based on these models. Challenges in building platforms with residential deployment constraints are discussed. BESI is currently deployed for an in-home study on dementia, and the results are presented to illustrate data collection procedures and system performance.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
200	Nonverbal behavior in multimodal systems	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3233795.3233803	No abstract available.		CE4	Livro.
201	Home Automation for an Independent Living: Investigating the Needs of Visually Impaired People	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3192714.3192823	Independence is essential for everyone and crucial for people with disabilities. Being able to perform the activities of daily living as autonomously as possible is an important step towards real inclusion and an independent life. Several technology-enhanced services and tools have been created to address special-needs users, but are they really used and appreciated by them? Sensors and radio frequency devices are increasingly exploited to develop solutions such as the smart home, aimed at improving the quality of life for all, including people with visual impairment. This paper collects blind users' expectations and habits regarding home automation technology through an online survey and face-to-face interviews. Specifically, 42 visually impaired people answered an accessible online questionnaire to provide more insight into their needs and preferences. Next, semi-structured short interviews conducted with a set of eight totally blind participants enabled the collection of relevant user requirements in order to better understand the obstacles experienced, and to design usable home automation and remote control systems. Results showed that the main requests regard increasing autonomy in everyday tasks and having more usability and flexibility when using remote home automation control. Thanks to the collected feedback, a set of general suggestions for designers and developers of home automation and remote control systems has been proposed in order to enhance accessibility and usability for the blind user.		CE5	Survey.
202	Index	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3233795.3233814	No abstract available.		CE4	Livro.

203	Preface	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3233795.3233796	No abstract available.		CE4	Livro.
204	Improving Emergency Healthcare Response using Real-Time Collaborative Technology	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3418094.3418118	Harnessing geospatial technologies (GPS, GIS, internet mapping and remote sensing) can promote collaboration of humans, environmental, and healthcare resources-for real-time decision support in emergency healthcare scenarios. Oftentimes, high death rates are recorded by emergency rescue workers due to infrastructural deficit and sparsity of ambulatory services within the patients' location. Also, acute shortage of health personnel may pose great risk to patients requiring emergency healthcare services, as limited knowledge of healthcare data can prevent proactive, just-in-time response to emergency, and dearth of appropriate healthcare policies. This study therefore proposes a geospatial recommender framework that connects patients with healthcare providers and other relevant stakeholders; to exploit and filter in context, emergency healthcare information and knowledge-for enhanced response strategy that minimizes fatalities among patients. We examine case study data within the African context and discuss infrastructural challenges, opportunities and design implications, to demonstrate the feasibility of our framework. The immediate benefit of the framework is enhanced specialty care for home-bound patients or in emergency cases where distance appears prohibitive. Our strategy will certainly scale up complex healthcare interventions to large populations, as a new paradigm for evidence-based intervention with state-of-the-art technology for optimized services is guaranteed.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
205	Embedded multimodal interfaces in robotics: applications, future trends, and societal implications	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3233795.3233810	No abstract available.		CE4	Livro.
206	A Holistic Multimedia System for Gastrointestinal Tract Disease Detection	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3083187.3083189	Analysis of medical videos for detection of abnormalities and diseases requires both high precision and recall, but also real-time processing for live feedback and scalability for massive screening of entire populations. Existing work on this field does not provide the necessary combination of retrieval accuracy and performance.; AB@In this paper, a multimedia system is presented where the aim is to tackle automatic analysis of videos from the human gastrointestinal (GI) tract. The system includes the whole pipeline from data collection, processing and analysis, to visualization. The system combines filters using machine learning, image recognition and extraction of global and local image features. Furthermore, it is built in a modular way so that it can easily be extended. At the same time, it is developed for efficient processing in order to provide real-time feedback to the doctors. Our experimental evaluation proves that our system has detection and localisation accuracy at least as good as existing systems for polyp detection, it is capable of detecting a wider range of diseases, it can analyze video in real-time, and it has a low resource consumption for scalability.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.

207	CSCW '17: Proceedings of the 2017 ACM Conference on Computer Supported Cooperative Work and Social Computing	https://dl.acm.org/doi/proceedings/10.1145/2998181	<p>Welcome to CSCW 2017, the ACM 2017 Conference on Computer Supported Cooperative Work and Social Computing! We are excited to welcome the CSCW community back to Portland, Oregon, where the second CSCW conference was held in 1988. Both Portland and CSCW have matured a great deal during the intervening 29 years. We hope that you will find that Portland provides a stimulating environment for our conference. CSCW is the premier venue for presenting research in the design and use of technologies that affect groups, organizations, communities, and networks. Bringing together top researchers and practitioners from academia and industry, CSCW explores the technical, social, material, and theoretical challenges of designing technology to support collaborative work and life activities. CSCW welcomes a diverse range of topics and research methodologies. Studies often involve the development and application of novel technologies and/or ethnographic studies that inform design practice or theory. The mission of the conference is to share research that advances the state of human knowledge and improves both the design of systems and the ways they are used. The diversity of work in our conference program reflects the diversity of technology use in people's work, social, and civic lives as well as the geographic and cultural diversity of contributors. As many of you know, CSCW follows a rigorous "revise and resubmit" review process that uses peer review to improve submitted papers while maintaining a high-quality threshold for final acceptance. We also help prepare the next generation of reviewers with a mentorship program in which students review papers under the guidance of an experienced reviewer. This year we have the largest CSCW program ever. We had 530 submitted papers and 183 were accepted for presentation at the conference. The program also includes 4 papers published in ACM Transactions on Human- Computer Interaction (TOCHI). In addition, we will feature 14 workshops, 56 posters, 12 demos, and 3 panels. Lili Cheng of Microsoft Research will open the conference, speaking on "Conversational AI & Lessons Learned." Our closing plenary will feature Jorge Cham, the creator of PhD Comics, who will talk about, "The Science Gap." We also welcome Paul Luff and Christian Heath from King's College as the recipients of this year's CSCW Lasting Impact award for their influential 1998 paper, "Mobility in Collaboration."</p>	CE4	Conferência
208	Introduction: toward the design, construction, and deployment of multimodal-multisensor interfaces	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3233795.3233797	No abstract available	CE4	Livro
209	Multimodal databases	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3233795.3233807	No abstract available	CE4	Livro
210	Commercialization of	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3233795.3233812	No abstract available	CE4	Livro

	multimodal systems				
211	Ergonomics for the design of multimodal interfaces	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3233795.3233804	No abstract available		CE4 Livro
212	Automotive multimodal human-machine interface	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3233795.3233809	No abstract available		CE4 Livro
213	Privacy concerns of multimodal sensor systems	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3233795.3233813	No abstract available		CE4 Livro
214	Simplicity and usability: lessons from a touchscreen electronic medical record system in Malawi	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2029976.2029990	No abstract available		CE4 Revista
215	Case study: predictive fairness to reduce misdemeanor recidivism through social service interventions	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3351095.3372863	The criminal justice system is currently ill-equipped to improve outcomes of individuals who cycle in and out of the system with a series of misdemeanor offenses. Often due to constraints of caseload and poor record linkage, prior interactions with an individual may not be considered when an individual comes back into the system, let alone in a proactive manner through the application of diversion programs. The Los Angeles City Attorney's Office recently created a new Recidivism Reduction and Drug Diversion unit (R2D2) tasked with reducing recidivism in this population. Here we describe a collaboration with this new unit as a case study for the incorporation of predictive equity into machine learning based decision making in a resource-constrained setting. The program seeks to improve outcomes by developing individually-tailored social service interventions (i.e., diversions, conditional plea agreements, stayed sentencing, or other favorable case disposition based on appropriate social service linkage rather than traditional sentencing methods) for individuals likely to experience subsequent interactions with the criminal justice system, a time and resource-intensive undertaking that necessitates an ability to focus resources on individuals most likely to be involved in a future case. Seeking to achieve both efficiency (through predictive accuracy) and equity (improving outcomes in traditionally under-served communities and working to		CE1 Não é da área da saúde.

			mitigate existing disparities in criminal justice outcomes), we discuss the equity outcomes we seek to achieve, describe the corresponding choice of a metric for measuring predictive fairness in this context, and explore a set of options for balancing equity and efficiency when building and selecting machine learning models in an operational public policy setting.			
216	Software platforms and toolkits for building multimodal systems and applications	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3233795.3233801	No abstract available.		CE4	Livro.
217	Precision and power issues in a medical sensor controller	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2801948.2801952	The continuous growing of the percentage of elderly people in total population the last decades has given significant boost to ehealth technology and applications that allow for the remote health monitoring of aging people, thus acting as a remedy to the explosive costs that would be otherwise needed for full medical coverage. In this context, we present in this paper an efficient ehealth platform based on a low-cost medical sensor controller system, the main features of which have been successfully enhanced in terms of flexibility, accuracy and power consumption so as to be able to provide wide coverage of tests/medical scenarios with the best possible reliability and low power consumption. A low-cost sensor controller capable of performing both simple and more advanced tests with increased accuracy forms the core of the system communicating with a Gateway installed in the patient's residence and a tablet or smart phone used for giving instructions to the patient by the medical supervisors. Appropriate processing and filtering algorithms are applied where necessary to enhance the accuracy of sensor measurements achieving substantial improvements close to the level of high-cost commercial ones. Furthermore, a combination of hardware and software techniques are employed which exploit at the best possible extent the idle intervals between measurements resulting in considerably lower power requirements and extension of the platform's portability.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
218	Challenge discussion: advancing multimodal dialogue	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3233795.3233802	No abstract available.		CE4	Livro.
219	DynAGreen: hierarchical dynamic energy efficient task assignment for wireless healthcare systems	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2221924.221932	Wireless sensor-based healthcare systems consist of hierarchically organized components with varying energy and performance capabilities, such as sensors, local aggregators (e.g. cell phones) and servers. This paper proposes a distributed graph-based approach to partition tasks across these various components with the goal of optimizing the available energy. State of the art implementations assume that all the data is gathered and forwarded for computation to the servers. We show in this work that significant gains in energy efficiency can be obtained if some of the processing tasks are assigned to sensors and local data aggregators. Our <i>DynAGreen</i> algorithm takes the graph associated with the workload and successively partitions it between the server, cell phones and sensors such that the overall system energy utilization for computing and communication tasks is minimized. Our experiments show that the		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.

			task assignment given by <i>DynAGreen</i> reduces the overall system energy by 30% with respect to an optimal static design time assignment when minor run time variations are considered.			
220	Prediction of Coronary Heart Disease using Machine Learning: An Experimental Analysis	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3342999.3343015	The field of medical analysis is often referred to be a valuable source of rich information. Coronary Heart Disease (CHD) is one of the major causes of death all around the world therefore early detection of CHD can help reduce these rates. The challenge lies in the complexity of the data and correlations when it comes to prediction using conventional techniques. The aim of this research is to use the historical medical data to predict CHD using Machine Learning (ML) technology. The scope of this research is limited to using three supervised learning techniques namely Naïve Bayes (NB), Support Vector Machine (SVM) and Decision Tree (DT), to discover correlations in CHD data that might help improving the prediction rate. Using the South African Heart Disease dataset of 462 instances, intelligent models are derived by the considered ML techniques using 10-fold cross validation. Empirical results using different performance evaluation measures report that probabilistic models derived by NB are promising in detecting CHD.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-abe
221	Acquiring semantic context for events from online resources	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/1899662.1899670	During the last few years, the amount of online descriptive information about places and their dynamics has reached reasonable dimension for many cities in the world. Such enriched information can now support semantic analysis of space, particularly in which respects to what <i>exists</i> there and what <i>happens</i> there. We present a methodology to automatically label places according to events that happen there. To achieve this we use Information Extraction techniques applied to online Web 2.0 resources such as Zvents and Boston Calendar. Wikipedia is also used as a resource to semantically enrich the tag vectors initially extracted. We describe the process by which these semantic vectors are obtained, present results of experimental analysis, and validated these with Amazon Mechanical Turk and a set of algorithms. To conclude, we discuss the strengths and weaknesses of the methodology.		CE1	Não é da área da saúde.
222	Situated interaction	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3233795.3233800	No abstract available.		CE4	Livro.
223	Multimodal integration for interactive conversational systems	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3233795.3233798	No abstract available.		CE4	Livro.
224	Code Nation: Personal Computing and the Learn to Program Movement in America	https://dl.acm.org/doi/book/10.1145/3368274	Code Nation explores the rise of software development as a social, cultural, and technical phenomenon in American history. The movement germinated in government and university labs during the 1950s, gained momentum through corporate and counterculture experiments in the 1960s and 1970s, and became a broad-based computer literacy movement in the 1980s. As personal computing came to the fore, learning to program was transformed by a groundswell of popular enthusiasm, exciting new platforms, and an array of commercial practices that have been further amplified by distributed computing and the Internet. The resulting society can be depicted as a “Code Nation”—a globally-connected world that is saturated with computer technology and enchanted by software and		CE4	Livro.

			its creation. Code Nation is a new history of personal computing that emphasizes the technical and business challenges that software developers faced when building applications for CP/M, MS-DOS, UNIX, Microsoft Windows, the Apple Macintosh, and other emerging platforms. It is a popular history of computing that explores the experiences of novice computer users, tinkerers, hackers, and power users, as well as the ideals and aspirations of leading computer scientists, engineers, educators, and entrepreneurs. Computer book and magazine publishers also played important, if overlooked, roles in the diffusion of new technical skills, and this book highlights their creative work and influence. Code Nation offers a “behind-the-scenes” look at application and operating-system programming practices, the diversity of historic computer languages, the rise of user communities, early attempts to market PC software, and the origins of “enterprise” computing systems. Code samples and over 80 historic photographs support the text. The book concludes with an assessment of contemporary efforts to teach computational thinking to young people.			
225	Sustainable Hacking: Characteristics of the Design and Adoption of Civic Hacking Projects	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3083671.3083706	Public organizations increasingly collaborate with civic-minded technologists to develop digital interventions for public issues through civic hacking projects. However, civic hacking cannot be a long-term solution without a proper handover and sustainability plan. In this study, we investigated how to design sustainable civic hacking projects for local governments and nonprofit organizations through intentional planning during the design process. We examined the design process of 16 civic hacking projects in a small Midwestern city in the United States. Drawing on observations, interviews, and documentation analysis, we argue that sustainable hacking should leverage off-the-shelf technologies and build good relationships with various stakeholders. Partners and technologists should also learn from each other about community practices and how to develop a data mindset. We discuss the design and practical implications to facilitate more sustainable civic hacking design processes for public organizations.		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.
226	Detecting Areas of Potential High Prevalence of Chagas in Argentina	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3308560.3316485	A map of potential prevalence of Chagas disease (ChD) with high spatial disaggregation is presented. It aims to detect areas outside the Gran Chaco ecoregion (hyperendemic for the ChD), characterized by high affinity with ChD and high health vulnerability. To quantify potential prevalence, we developed several indicators: an Affinity Index which quantifies the degree of linkage between endemic areas of ChD and the rest of the country. We also studied favorable habitability conditions for <i>Triatoma infestans</i> , looking for areas where the predominant materials of floors, roofs and internal ceilings favor the presence of the disease vector. We studied determinants of a more general nature that can be encompassed under the concept of Health Vulnerability Index. These determinants are associated with access to health providers and the socio-economic level of different segments of the population. Finally we constructed a Chagas Potential Prevalence Index (ChPPI) which combines the affinity index, the health vulnerability index, and the population density. We show and discuss the maps obtained. These maps are intended to assist public health specialists, decision makers of public health policies and public officials in the development of cost-effective strategies to improve access to diagnosis and treatment of ChD.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
227	When blazing a trail leads over the	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/1449956.1450031	At SIGUCCS 2007, one of the themes promoted by James Hilton of the University of Virginia was that in the world of IT at colleges and universities, we are likely to see more change happening more quickly than ever before, and that we need to learn ways to make the change happen as quickly and as painlessly as possible. A variety of circumstances led UVA to make a switch in its enterprise calendaring		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.

	mountainside cliff: lessons learned from our first rapid deployment		system between December 4, 2007 and January 15, 2008. Learn about the reasons behind this change, the obstacles we encountered, the user experience of the change and the lessons we learned in our first rapid change.			
228	Initial study and statistical analyses of specialization database	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3401895.3401927	This work presents a study that tracked data generated from distance education systems, and made use of these data, often neglected, to produce information and knowledge about the system itself as well as the involved people. The strategy presented go from the basic data handle on the distance education systems, using statistical applications methods, applied for data processing. The presented activities aim to improve the quality of the service offered on online courses, and also help solve some issues, for instance the student's evasion. It is also presenting a case study where statistical methods were applied to deal with the student's evasion in a real distance education system. The main goal was to start the use of learning analytics concepts.		CE1	Não é da área da saúde.
229	Leveraging technology to improve quality of mental health care in Karnataka	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3462741.3466652	Health is multidimensional and “there is no health without mental health”. We document ongoing technology-enabled initiatives for enhancing mental health care in the state of Karnataka. Multi-disciplinary teams have collaborated on a set of four projects to design and deploy digital technologies across different parts of the healthcare continuum, addressing beneficiaries (patients and care-givers), different levels of mental health care providers (doctors, social workers, etc..) and health administrators, alike. The vision is to define and develop a digital platform for mental health care and services within the state of Karnataka and scalable across India.		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.
230	Multimedia and Medicine: Teammates for Better Disease Detection and Survival	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2964284.2976760	Health care has a long history of adopting technology to save lives and improve the quality of living. Visual information is frequently applied for disease detection and assessment, and the established fields of computer vision and medical imaging provide essential tools. It is, however, a misconception that disease detection and assessment are provided exclusively by these fields and that they provide the solution for all challenges. Integration and analysis of data from several sources, real-time processing, and the assessment of usefulness for end-users are core competences of the multimedia community and are required for the successful improvement of health care systems. We have conducted initial investigations into two use cases surrounding diseases of the gastrointestinal (GI) tract, where the detection of abnormalities provides the largest chance of successful treatment if the initial observation of disease indicators occurs before the patient notices any symptoms. Although such detection is typically provided visually by applying an endoscope, we are facing a multitude of new multimedia challenges that differ between use cases. In real-time assistance for colonoscopy, we combine sensor information about camera position and direction to aid in detecting, investigate means for providing support to doctors in unobtrusive ways, and assist in reporting. In the area of large-scale capsular endoscopy, we investigate questions of scalability, performance and energy efficiency for the recording phase, and combine video summarization and retrieval questions for analysis.		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.
231	DEsigning a Secure Systems Engineering	https://dl.acm.org/doi/book/10.5555/3278160	The goal of the DEsigning a Secure Systems Competition (DESSEC) workshop was to produce a report that contains as complete a specification as possible for three or more competitions that would encourage innovation in how secure systems are built.		CE4	Livro.

	Competition: Workshop Report				
232	WWW '19: Companion Proceedings of The 2019 World Wide Web Conference	https://dl.acm.org/doi/proceedings/10.1145/3308560	It is our great pleasure to welcome you to <I>The Web Conference 2019</I>. The Web Conference is the premier venue focused on understanding the current state and the evolution of the Web through the lens of computer science, computational social science, economics, policy, and many other disciplines. The 2019 edition of the conference is a reflection point as we celebrate the 30th anniversary of the Web.		CE4 Conferência
233	Identification of Imminent Suicide Risk Among Young Adults using Text Messages	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3173574.3173987	Suicide is the second leading cause of death among young adults but the challenges of preventing suicide are significant because the signs often seem invisible. Research has shown that clinicians are not able to reliably predict when someone is at greatest risk. In this paper, we describe the design, collection, and analysis of text messages from individuals with a history of suicidal thoughts and behaviors to build a model to identify periods of suicidality (i.e., suicidal ideation and non-fatal suicide attempts). By reconstructing the timeline of recent suicidal behaviors through a retrospective clinical interview, this study utilizes a prospective research design to understand if text communications can predict periods of suicidality versus depression. Identifying subtle clues in communication indicating when someone is at heightened risk of a suicide attempt may allow for more effective prevention of suicide.		CE1 Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
234	A Craft Approach to Health Awareness in Children	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2901790.2901888	Children in the USA are increasingly at risk for a vast array of health problems due to poor dietary habits and lack of physical activity. In recent years, a burgeoning landscape of wearable and mobile health technologies in the form of activity trackers and fitness applications have focused on addressing this problem. While these solutions have had some measure of success with children, there is also evidence that youngsters are not readily adopting the types of fitness implements that adults find useful. In this paper, we present a computational toolkit that blends craft and health, permitting children to craft their own tangible health visualizations based on data from an accompanying wearable device. We also present the results of an encouraging 2-month study conducted with middle school children. The results suggest that craft could potentially serve as a gateway to healthful thinking in children.		CE1 Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
235	Investigating quality requirements for blockchain-based healthcare systems	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/09/WETSEB.2019.00014	Healthcare is a data-intensive domain, once a considerable amount of data is daily produced due to monitoring patients, managing identities, producing medical records and processing medical insurance claims. Hence, security, besides other quality requirements, is prominent to preserve the confidentiality and integrity of such data. Blockchain technology has received attention as a mean to support secure transactions and records, including in the healthcare domain. The main contribution of this paper is providing preliminary results of an investigation on the recent literature on how the inherent characteristics of blockchain can enhance or hinder particular quality requirements in healthcare systems. We provide a preliminary analysis of five essential quality requirements for healthcare domain, besides pointing for advances that must still be achieved.		CE5 Revisão da literatura.
236	MotionTalk: personalized home rehabilitatio	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2649387.2649430	Physical injury, stroke, trauma, traumatic brain injury and spinal cord injury rank among the top causes of disability. There are a total of 54 million people in the US requiring rehabilitative assistance of which 15.3 million people are in the age groups of 18-44. However, the compliance rate for patients performing rehabilitation exercises in the home environment is poor. In this paper, we design and prototype a		CE1 Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.

	n system for assisting patients with impaired mobility		personalized home rehabilitation system, MotionTalk, for the real time quantitative assessment of mobility. Performance of rehabilitation is designed to be assessed using the changes in mobility, reflected in the exercises performed by patients at home with respect to the same exercises performed in the clinic. Our system is capable of capturing motion using Microsoft Kinect and analyzing the position and rotation information to give scores for assessing rehabilitation progress. In comparison to conventional rehabilitation systems, MotionTalk is an inexpensive (<\$150 compared to conventional systems costing >\$1000), less intrusive and personalized home rehabilitation system, which was developed and tested using data from able-bodied volunteers at Georgia Institute of Technology.			
237	Design principles for health wearables	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3131201.3131205	As wearables become increasingly prevalent, there is a concurrent and growing expectation that we use these devices to track and monitor our bodily states in order to be responsible "biocitizens." To mitigate this, some health, design, and usability scholars have advocated for greater patient control over health data. To support these efforts, this article offers a set of criteria for analyzing wearables, criteria that account for the handling of data and user connections via wearables as they relate to three priorities: accessibility, adaptability, and iterability. These are meant to support analyses that will clarify the ways wearables can more ethically serve end-users'---that is, patients' and wearers'---emerging needs, rather than primarily serving the intermediary goals of care delivery personnel and systems to monitor and manage patient behavior. To do this, this article addresses the usability of wearables as it relates to other critical care issues, such as "information integrity" and enabling patients to maintain their own health records and participate in shared decision making.		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.
238	TWINY emotional logging	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2641248.2641275	Taking stress out of people's lives is a great step to a better life in the future. To create a healthier lifestyle it is important to prevent stress related illnesses. The goal of this project is to make people aware of their state of mind and conscious of how they feel. Twiny is an elastic bracelet that gathers physical parameters through sensors: connecting emotions to physical state, Twiny gives the possibility to learn how to control mood, organizing time and trying to make people feel comfortable. Matching feelings data with calendar and health state, Twiny is able to build a grid of feelings, suggesting how to react to a bad mood or, for instance a constant migraine. Twiny attempts to correlate data down to every physical rash caused from stress to the body. Making people aware of their unconscious feelings will help them build a better lifestyle. Twiny, which wirelessly sends data to an application, allows users to control their own parameters every time they need.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
239	Appropriation by unanticipated users: looking beyond design intent and expected use	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2441776.2441949	Research in CSCW has demonstrated that people use technology in inventive ways, yet little work investigates the adoption and adaptation of collaborative technologies by unanticipated users. In this paper, we present a study investigating an unanticipated user group's appropriation of a leaning management system, CTools. This group of users, staff at a large research university, has adapted the system, which was designed to support student-content-faculty interactions at the University of Michigan. We present the User/Use Technology Appropriation Matrix (UTAM) as a way to frame our understanding of users and their system use. Based on findings from system log data and surveys, we show that staff use the system similarly to students and faculty, though they value the tools and work affordances differently in their varied work contexts. We discuss these findings, how UTAM can be used to frame these findings, and suggestions for future research.		CE1	Não é da área da saúde.

240	A low-tech sensing system for particulate pollution	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2540930.2540955	We present an ultra low-cost sensing system, which enables participants to see and reflect on the particulates in their air. Drawing on prior work in paper computing, we introduce small sensors for particulate pollution that can be easily assembled from common paper materials for less than \$1 USD, and mailed by regular postal service to residents of entire neighborhoods, cities, or geographic regions. Recipients collect particulate samples using these sensors and mail them back to a central location, where the particles are viewed and analyzed via a microscope. The data, which includes rich images of actual air pollution particles, can then be broadcast to larger audiences. This paper details the design of our system and its deployment with a local air quality activist community. We conclude by highlighting the tradeoffs between high-tech and low-tech sensing, and suggest opportunities for tangible interaction to support rich, new ways of seeing our environment.		CE1	Não é da área da saúde.
241	News	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/376451.376458	No abstract available.		CE4	Revista.
242	From Cyber Terrorism to Cyber Peacekeeping: Are we there yet?	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3437120.3437335	In Cyberspace nowadays, there is a burst of information that everyone has access. However, apart from the advantages the Internet offers, it also hides numerous dangers for both people and nations. Cyberspace has a dark side, including terrorism, bullying, and other types of violence. Cyberwarfare is a kind of virtual war that causes the same destruction that a physical war would also do. In this article, we discuss what Cyberterrorism is and how it can lead to Cyberwarfare.		CE1	Não é da área da saúde.
243	Blockchain-empowered Data-driven Networks: A Survey and Outlook	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3446373	The paths leading to future networks are pointing towards a data-driven paradigm to better cater to the explosive growth of mobile services as well as the increasing heterogeneity of mobile devices, many of which generate and consume large volumes and variety of data. These paths are also hampered by significant challenges in terms of security, privacy, services provisioning, and network management. Blockchain, which is a technology for building distributed ledgers that provide an immutable log of transactions recorded in a distributed network, has become prominent recently as the underlying technology of cryptocurrencies and is revolutionizing data storage and processing in computer network systems. For future data-driven networks (DDNs), blockchain is considered as a promising solution to enable the secure storage, sharing, and analytics of data, privacy protection for users, robust, trustworthy network control, and decentralized routing and resource managements. However, many important challenges and open issues remain to be addressed before blockchain can be deployed widely to enable future DDNs. In this article, we present a survey on the existing research works on the application of blockchain technologies in computer networks and identify challenges and potential solutions in the applications of blockchains in future DDNs. We identify application scenarios in which future blockchain-empowered DDNs could improve the efficiency and security, and generally the effectiveness of network services.		CE5	Survey.
244	Quitty: using technology to persuade smokers to quit	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2639189.2639195	Health is an important topic in HCI research with an increasing amount of health risks surrounding individuals and society at large. It is well known that smoking cigarettes can have serious health implications. The importance of this problem motivates investigation into the use of technology to encourage behavior change. Our study was designed to gather empirical knowledge about the role a "quitting app" can play in persuading people to quit smoking. Our purpose-built app <i>Quitty</i> introduces different content types from		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.

			different content sources to study how they are perceived and motivate health behavior change. Findings from our field study show that tailored content and push-messages are considered the most important for persuading people to stop smoking. Based on our empirical findings, we propose six guidelines on how to design mobile applications to persuade smokers to quit.			
245	Sweet Home: understanding diabetes management via a chinese online community	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2556288.2557344	China has overtaken India and the U.S. as host to the largest diabetic population in the world. Many problems exist in the Chinese healthcare system and very small number of diabetes patients receives treatment. Our paper reports on a case study through the lens of an online diabetes patient community, Sweet Home. We conducted participant observations, text analysis, and interviews, to understand the health management of patients at Sweet Home. Our findings reveal that patients' understanding of diabetes, their choice of treatments, their routine management, and their interactions with others (in the physical world) and among themselves (in the online world) are influenced by many factors: belief in traditional Chinese versus western medicine, cultural and social norms regarding social eating and drinking, conflicts over self-images, and responses to comments and pressures of coworkers. That is, social context may significantly affect patients' behaviors and each individual patient's actions may also help reshape the social context. We draw out implications for how our society as a whole may respond to these issues, from the perspective of public health, education, and information technology design.		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.
246	Experiences with bulk SMS for health financing in Uganda	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2212776.212816	Short message service (SMS, aka text messaging) is a low-cost and effective means of communication for organizations attempting to maintain contact with many people. In this paper we look at the deployment and of a bulk mobile text-messaging platform (Bulk SMS), conceived and commissioned by a health non-governmental organization (NGO) for use in communicating with the 100+ private health facilities. We show how the platform emerged from existing practices, the features and expectations of the system, and the ways in which it was used. Common failure points include infrastructural limitations, human error, and unexpected use cases. We find that 1) the use of SMS as a media enables new types of communication, and 2) SMS alone is not sufficient for maintaining relationships within the NGO program.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
247	I know what you did last summer... an investigation into remnant data on USB storage devices sold in Australia in 2015	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2843043.2843356	The demand for portable digital data storage has increased with the evolution and advancement in consumer electronic devices. USB storage devices, also referred to as USB sticks, pen drives, flash drives, thumb drives, and key drives, have replaced many other portable storage. With the evolution of these devices, an increased use for data transportation has been seen for both private and commercial data. USB storage capacity has increased during the past decades with capacities up to one terabyte available today. Such devices are increasingly popular given their robustness, low power consumption, rapid response rates, non-volatile nature, and ease of transportation. This study obtained second hand USB flash memory storage devices, purchased from eBay Australia over a period of seven months, to determine whether there were any traces of data on the devices, and whether or not an attempt had been made to securely wipe the devices. If data fragments were recovered, it was assessed to see if there was a sufficient volume and sensitivity of data to be of value to anyone with malicious intent. The findings from the research show that in the majority of the cases, the USB flash memory storage devices retained a large volume of data. Concurring with outcomes from previous studies in 2009 and 2011, the devices investigated in this study, owned by both individuals and organisations, were used to store highly sensitive and confidential data. This data was not		CE1	Não é da área da saúde.

			permanently nor securely destroyed prior to disposal (by sale) of the devices. Such incidents highlight the failure to meet regulatory obligations with regard to privacy legislation in Australia.			
248	Risks to the public in computers and related systems	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/505894.505900	No abstract available.		CE4	Livro
249	Inference Attacks on Property-Preserving Encrypted Databases	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2810103.2813651	Many encrypted database (EDB) systems have been proposed in the last few years as cloud computing has grown in popularity and data breaches have increased. The state-of-the-art EDB systems for relational databases can handle SQL queries over encrypted data and are competitive with commercial database systems. These systems, most of which are based on the design of CryptDB (SOSP 2011), achieve these properties by making use of property-preserving encryption schemes such as deterministic (DTE) and order-preserving encryption (OPE). In this paper, we study the concrete security provided by such systems. We present a series of attacks that recover the plaintext from DTE- and OPE-encrypted database columns using only the encrypted column and publicly-available auxiliary information. We consider well-known attacks, including frequency analysis and sorting, as well as new attacks based on combinatorial optimization. We evaluate these attacks empirically in an electronic medical records (EMR) scenario using real patient data from 200 U.S. hospitals. When the encrypted database is operating in a steady-state where enough encryption layers have been peeled to permit the application to run its queries, our experimental results show that an alarming amount of sensitive information can be recovered. In particular, our attacks correctly recovered certain OPE-encrypted attributes (e.g., age and disease severity) for more than 80% of the patient records from 95% of the hospitals; and certain DTE- encrypted attributes (e.g., sex, race, and mortality risk) for more than 60% of the patient records from more than 60% of the hospitals.		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.